

**WEAK GRAVITATIONAL LENSING SYSTEMATIC ERRORS IN
THE DARK ENERGY SURVEY**

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¹“Saludo a esta Realidad Sat, en la que todos los seres animados e inanimados se manifiestan como si tuvieran una existencia independiente, permanecen durante unos instantes y desaparecen para siempre. Me inclino ante esta Conciencia Chit, que toma la triple forma de conocedor, conocimiento y conocido, desdoblándose como el que ve, la visión y lo visto, y transformándose en el actor, lo hecho y la acción. Rindo culto a esta Felicidad absoluta Ananda, que es la vida de todos los seres cuya dichosa manifestación emana del que contempla la espuma de este océano de felicidad”. Yoga Vasistha

ABSTRACT
WEAK GRAVITATIONAL LENSING SYSTEMATIC ERRORS IN THE DARK
ENERGY SURVEY

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Dark energy is one of the most important unsolved problems in modern Physics, and weak gravitational lensing (WL) by mass structures along the line of sight (“cosmic shear”) is a promising technique to learn more about its nature. However, WL is subject to numerous systematic errors which induce biases in measured cosmological parameters and prevent the development of its full potential. In this thesis, we advance the understanding of WL systematics in the context of the Dark Energy Survey (DES).

We develop a testing suite to assess the performance of the shapelet-based DES WL measurement pipeline. We determine that the measurement bias of the parameters of our Point Spread Function (PSF) model scales as $(S/N)^{-2}$, implying that a PSF $S/N > 75$ is needed to satisfy DES requirements. PSF anisotropy suppression also satisfies the requirements for source galaxies with $S/N \gtrsim 45$. For low-noise, marginally-resolved exponential galaxies, the shear calibration errors are up to $\sim 0.06\%$ (for shear values $\lesssim 0.075$). Galaxies with $S/N \gtrsim 75$ present $\sim 1\%$ errors, sufficient for first-year DES data. However, more work is needed to satisfy full-area DES requirements, especially in the high-noise regime.

We then implement tests to validate the high accuracy of the map between pixel coordinates and sky coordinates (astrometric solution), which is crucial to detect the

required number of galaxies for WL in stacked images.

We also study the effect of atmospheric dispersion on cosmic shear experiments such as DES and the Large Synoptic Survey Telescope (LSST) in the four *griz* bands. For DES (LSST), we find systematics in the *g* and *r* (*g*, *r*, and *i*) bands that are larger than required. We find that a simple linear correction in galaxy color is accurate enough to reduce dispersion shear systematics to insignificant levels in the *r* (*i*) band for DES (LSST). More complex corrections will likely reduce the systematic cosmic-shear errors below statistical errors for LSST *r* band. However, *g*-band dispersion effects remain large enough for induced systematics to dominate the statistical error of both surveys, so cosmic-shear measurements should rely on the redder bands.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Physical cosmology can be defined as the study of the physical Universe as a whole. Since the beginning of recorded history, humanity has been fascinated by questions such as: Where do we come from? Why are we here? What is the origin of everything we observe? These questions are not trivial, and some of them spark deep philosophical debates. Cosmology tries to address the subset of these questions that concern the physical world in which we live, through the use of the scientific method. The questions we address in this case are also very deep and interesting: Did the Universe have a beginning? If so, will it have an end? What is the Universe made of? How has it evolved with time? Is it spatially infinite? As in the rest of the sciences, the cornerstones of cosmology are experiments and observations, which eventually lead to the formulation of a mathematical model capable of explaining existing observations and making falsifiable predictions.

The quality and quantity of the observations of the Universe have been gradually increasing over time. Technological advances in the last century have been especially important, such as the invention of the charge coupled device (CCD) and the construction of ground- and space- based telescopes to probe the Universe at all wavelengths. The finite speed of light has allowed us to look deeper into the past history of the Universe and study its evolution.

Observations of the Universe led to the formulation of a cosmological model called the Hot Big Bang (HBB) theory. In this model, the Universe started in a hot, dense state where all matter and radiation were clustered together, and it has been expanding and cooling ever since. However, HBB cosmology presented some problems that required the introduction of an earlier period of accelerated expansion, called inflation. Moreover, as observations became more accurate and numerous, the existence of two extra components that make up $\sim 95\%$ of all the contents of the Universe, dark matter and dark energy, was established (Biello and Caldwell, 2006; Frieman et al., 2008). Currently, dark energy is causing the Universe to undergo an epoch of accelerated expansion (as inflation did in the past). Modern theories fail to provide a satisfactory explanation of the nature of either dark energy or dark matter.

Dark energy has been identified as one of the most important problems of not only modern cosmology, but of modern physics (Turner, 2001; NRC, 2003; Albrecht et al., 2006). The study of both dark matter and dark energy could ultimately lead to the discovery of a new fundamental particle or new spatial dimensions, or even to the formulation of a theory of gravity beyond Einstein's General Relativity, which lies at the heart of cosmology and has been successfully tested during the past 100 years. Substantial effort is currently being made by researchers all over the world to address these two problems.

One of the main and most promising techniques to learn more about the nature of dark energy is weak gravitational lensing (WL) (Albrecht et al., 2006; Peacock et al., 2006). Gravitational lensing is the bending of light from distant sources (such as galaxies or quasars) by mass concentrations in the Universe, distorting the shapes of the source objects. By measuring these shapes, we can relate the statistical properties of the distortion caused by weak lensing to the statistical properties of the dark matter distributions at different epochs in the evolution of the Universe. By studying the change over time of this dark matter distribution, we can infer properties about dark energy. However, the weak lensing measurement process is not trivial, and several systematic errors have to be correctly understood and modeled in order to be able

to recover the lensing signal, which is of the order of $1 - 2\%$ of the intrinsic galaxies' shapes.

The main purpose of this thesis is to characterize some of the systematic errors to which the weak lensing measurement is subject, in the frame of the Dark Energy Survey (DES)¹ experiment, expected to start operations before the end of 2012. In this introductory chapter we explain the basic observations and theory that provide the foundation of the Standard Cosmological Model, emphasizing the basics of weak lensing theory, and providing the definitions and mathematical relationships that we will use in subsequent chapters. In Chapter 2 we describe the testing suite that we developed to assess the performance of the core of the shape measurement pipeline that will be used in DES. We identify the circumstances under which the pipeline satisfies the requirements for DES, and the areas where improvements should be made. Chapter 3 describes the implementation of a series of tests designed to validate that the mapping between the coordinates of our optical detector and the sky coordinates (crucial to the use of galaxies measured in multiple exposures) is accurate enough for WL science. Finally, in Chapter 4 we show how atmospheric dispersion can bias weak lensing measurements and discuss possible corrections. The work presented in Chapter 4 was accepted for publication in the *Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific*.

1.1 Fundamental Observations

1.1.1 Hubble's Law: the redshift of galaxies is proportional to their distances

Galaxies' spectra have several absorption and emission lines that are created by the gas and stars they contain. If we pick one of these lines and measure its wavelength, we will observe that this value differs from what we would measure in a laboratory

¹www.darkenergysurvey.org/

on Earth. Using these two measurements, we say that the galaxy has a *redshift*, z , defined by:

$$z \equiv \frac{\lambda_{\text{obs}} - \lambda_{\text{em}}}{\lambda_{\text{em}}}, \quad (1.1)$$

where λ_{obs} is the wavelength of the line measured by an observer on Earth and λ_{em} is the wavelength emitted at the galaxy's original position. In 1929, the American astronomer Edwin Hubble was the first to study the relationship between the redshifts of galaxies, z , and their distances, r , from us. He found the following linear relationship, known as *Hubble's Law* (see Figure 1.1a for a modern Hubble diagram determined by using Type Ia Supernovae):

$$z = \frac{H_0}{c}r, \quad (1.2)$$

where H_0 is *Hubble's constant*, one of the most important parameters in the current Standard Cosmological model (Section 1.2). For small redshifts, the relationship between z and the apparent radial velocities of galaxies v can be written as $z = v/c$, in which case Hubble's Law takes the following form:

$$v = H_0 r. \quad (1.3)$$

Recent measurements indicate that the value of Hubble's constant is $H_0 = 73.8 \pm 2.4 \text{ km s}^{-1}\text{Mpc}^{-1}$ (Riess et al., 2011). The Hubble constant may also be expressed as $H_0 = 100h \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$, where $h = 0.738$. The fact that galaxies are moving away from each other supports the idea of the Big Bang model, in which the Universe is expanding and cooling down from an initial hot and dense state. Note that the inverse of the Hubble constant has units of time: $H_0^{-1} \approx 13.8 \pm 1.4 \text{ Gyr}$. This time-scale is known as the *Hubble time*, and it is an estimate of the age of the Universe. An estimate of the size of the observable Universe is given by the *Hubble distance*: $cH_0^{-1} \approx 6200 \text{ Mpc}$.

(a) Hubble diagram. Credit: Jha (2002)

(b) The 7-year temperature power spectrum from WMAP. Credit: Larson et al. (2011)

(c) Relative abundances from BBN compared to WMAP measurements. Image taken from http://map.gsfc.nasa.gov/universe/bb_tests_ele.html

Figure 1.1: Observational pillars of the the HBB theory: a) Hubble expansion, b) Cosmic Microwave Background, c) Light-elements abundance.

1.1.2 The Cosmic Microwave Background

Using a microwave antenna in 1965, Robert Wilson and Arno Penzias found that the sky is full of an isotropic background of blackbody radiation. In the Big Bang theory, the Universe was very hot and dense in the past. As it expands, it cools, and the Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) is the remnant radiation left over from that hot past. It was emitted when the Universe was about 400,000 years old and about a factor of 1/1,100 its present size. Thus, by carefully studying the physical properties of this radiation, we can learn about the Universe on large scales at very

early times.

The energy spectrum of the CMB was predicted by the Big Bang theory to follow a thermal or blackbody spectrum. This was confirmed by the FIRAS instrument on the Cosmic Microwave Background Explorer (COBE) (Smoot et al., 1992). It is “the most precise blackbody spectrum measured in Nature” (White, 1999), and its temperature was found to be $T_0 = 2.725 \pm 0.0001\text{K}$. The measurements performed by COBE marked the beginning of the the era of “precision Cosmology”, and the 2006 Nobel Prize in Physics was awarded to the principal investigators of the project.

The CMB is not perfectly isotropic, and very small temperature fluctuations on the order of 1 part in 10^5 were measured in detail by the Wilkinson Microwave Anisotropy Probe (WMAP) (Komatsu et al., 2011). These anisotropies are imprints of density fluctuations in the early Universe which eventually gave rise to the structures we observe today (galaxies, filaments, clusters of galaxies, etc.). The structure of the power spectrum of the temperature anisotropy as a function of (inverse) angular scale is affected by the initial oscillations of the baryon-photon plasma of the early Universe (Baryon Acoustic Oscillations, BAO), and the positions and relative amplitudes of the peaks of the spectrum contain a wealth of information about the cosmological parameters of the Standard Cosmological model (Komatsu et al., 2011) (Figure 1.1b). WMAP observations, for instance, imply that the curvature of space (Section 1.2.1) is within 0.6% of flat (using the value of h quoted above).

1.1.3 Abundance of Light Elements

During the first three minutes after the Big Bang, the Universe was very hot and filled with a plasma of neutrons, photons, electrons, protons, and positrons (baryon-photon plasma). As the Universe cooled down, the neutrons decayed into protons and electrons or combined with protons to make deuterium. Lithium was also formed. Heavier elements could not have formed at this point of the evolution of the Universe because neutrons decay in about 600 seconds and their number density decreased

with time as the Universe expanded. The process of formation of light elements is referred to as Big Bang Nucleosynthesis (BBN), and the HBB theory predicts the abundances of each one as a function of the fraction of ordinary matter in the early Universe. Using data from the CMB (WMAP satellite), we can determine the latter ($\approx 4\%$) and then compare the resulting predictions with actual measurements. There is agreement between the observed abundances and predictions (Figure 1.1c).

Hubble's Law, the CMB, and the abundance of light elements are considered to be the three observational pillars of the HBB model.

1.2 Standard Cosmological Model

In general, when constructing a cosmological model, we use four main hypotheses (Ruiz-Lapuente, 2010):

- A theory of gravity.
- A description of the matter-energy components of the Universe and their non-gravitational interactions.
- A symmetry hypothesis.
- A hypothesis on the topology (global structure) of the Universe.

The standard cosmological model we use is based on Einstein's General Relativity (GR) as the theory of gravity. The Universe is assumed to be composed of the fields (and their normal modes of excitation or particles) of the Standard Model of Particle Physics plus two extra components: dark matter and dark energy. The latter two, when combined, make up almost 95% of the matter-energy contents of the Universe. Dark matter and dark energy, so far, do not have any physical explanation, making them some of the most important unsolved problems in modern physics. The Copernican Principle is another crucial assumption, which states that humans are

not privileged observers of the Universe. If we combine this symmetry hypothesis with the observations that suggest that on large scales ($\gtrsim 100$ Mpc) the Universe is isotropic, we can prove that the Universe is generally homogeneous and isotropic about any other point². This condition is known as the Cosmological Principle, and it is of invaluable help in solving the highly non-linear field equations resulting from GR, allowing us to model the matter in Universe as an ideal fluid and thus derive the equations that describe it on large scales (*i.e.*, the Friedmann Equations, see below). Perturbation theory then allows us to go beyond the homogeneous Universe and derive a general framework for the formation of the highly inhomogeneous structure we observe (planets, stars, galaxies, galaxy clusters, etc.) through the *gravitational instability* paradigm.³ Finally, it is generally assumed that spatial sections are simply connected⁴ and that the topology of the Universe is the simplest one compatible with its geometry, even though, so far, there are not direct measurements of a cosmic topology (although see Levin (2002) for possible hints of topology on the CMB).

The observations and conclusions that we presented in Section 1.1 have led to the construction of a cosmological model known as the Hot Big Bang model. This model, however, required the introduction of a mechanism, known as *inflation* (Guth, 1981), that solved the so-called *flatness* and *horizon* problems. The horizon problem is the fact that different regions of the Universe have the same physical properties (as shown by the CMB) even when they were not in causal contact in the past. The flatness problem is related to the fact that a flat Universe at the present time implies that it was also flat in the past, requiring a delicate fine tuning in the energy densities of the components of early Universe. Inflation states that the very early Universe ($t \approx 10^{-34}$ s) underwent a period of accelerated expansion whose dynamics are those of a scalar field ϕ slowly rolling on a potential $V(\phi)$ (Liddle and Lyth, 2000). Inflation

²In this sense, the Cosmological Principle is a stronger hypothesis, since it makes predictions even for regions of the Universe that cannot be observed.

³Gravitational instability is the mechanism through which regions with matter overdensity increase their amplitude over time due to their self-gravity, while underdense regions become more void.

⁴That is to say, any simple closed curve can be continuously reduced to a single point.

also provides a mechanism to seed the matter perturbations (see Section 1.3) that eventually evolved into the current large scale structure of the Universe.

The resulting Standard Cosmological model is known as Lambda-Cold Dark Matter model (Λ CDM). It incorporates the successes of the HBB cosmology (such as BBN) and the new observations that suggest that we live in a flat, accelerating Universe that experienced an early period of rapid expansion through the inflationary scenario. In this model, inflation was also responsible for amplifying the quantum fluctuations that would later turn into density inhomogeneities. The Λ CDM model states that the Universe is composed of $\sim 70\%$ of dark energy (whose simplest form is the cosmological constant Λ), $\sim 25\%$ of cold dark matter (“cold” as opposed to relativistic or “hot” dark matter), and $\sim 5\%$ of the ordinary matter that makes up humans, planets, and stars.

1.2.1 The Smooth and Expanding Universe

The basic mathematical entity to describe the geometry of the Universe is the symmetric rank-2 metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$. It can be thought of, roughly speaking, as a generalization of the classical gravitational field of Newtonian dynamics. In the standard cosmological model it is also assumed that we live in a 4-dimensional Riemannian manifold (mathematical representation of spacetime), whose causal and geometric structure are described by the metric. Once a metric is defined, notions like distance, curvature and volume can be defined. For a spatially homogeneous and isotropic expanding Universe, the metric is given by $g_{\mu\nu} = \text{diag}(-1, a^2, a^2, a^2)$.

The function $a(t)$ is the *scale factor*, and it represents the relative expansion of the Universe. It is usually set to 1 at the present time. The scale factor is a function of the cosmological proper time t (or simply cosmic time), and it is the time measured by observers who see the Universe expanding uniformly around them. It is inversely related to the redshift:

$$a(t) = \frac{1}{1 + z(t)}. \tag{1.4}$$

The distance between two points in spacetime is given in terms of the metric by the line element, which is invariant under change of coordinates:

$$ds^2 = g_{\mu\nu} dx^\mu dx^\nu, \quad \mu, \nu \in [0, 3]. \quad (1.5)$$

In the previous equation we have assumed the Einstein convention on summation over repeated indices. In spherical comoving (see Equation [1.24] below) coordinates, (χ, θ, ϕ) , the line element reads:

$$ds^2 = -c^2 dt^2 + a^2(t) \left[d\chi^2 + f_\kappa(\chi^2)(d\theta^2 + \sin^2(\theta)d\phi^2) \right], \quad (1.6)$$

where c represents the speed of light, and the *curvature constant*, κ , represents the three possible geometries of the spatial part of the metric: $\kappa = 0$ is a flat, Euclidean Universe; $\kappa > 0$ is a closed Universe with positive curvature (*e.g.*, a 3-Sphere); and $\kappa < 0$ is an open Universe with negative curvature (*e.g.*, a saddle). The function $f_\kappa(\chi)$ is given by:

$$f_\kappa(\chi) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\sqrt{\kappa}} \sin(\sqrt{\kappa}\chi) & \text{for } \kappa > 0 \\ \chi & \text{for } \kappa = 0 \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{-\kappa}} \sinh(\sqrt{-\kappa}\chi) & \text{for } \kappa < 0, \end{cases} \quad (1.7)$$

In these units (where $a(t)$ is dimensionless), χ has units of distance, and κ units of length⁻². This metric was independently derived by Friedmann, Lemaître, Robertson, and Walker in the 1920s and 1930s, and therefore it is known as the FLRW metric.

Particles in space that are not subject to any external force move in trajectories $x^\mu(\lambda)$ along geodesics (which are the generalizations of Euclidean straight lines), found by solving the *geodesic equation*:

$$\frac{d^2 x^\mu}{d\lambda^2} + \Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^\mu \frac{dx^\alpha}{d\lambda} \frac{dx^\beta}{d\lambda} = 0. \quad (1.8)$$

The Cristoffel symbols, $\Gamma_{\rho\sigma}^\mu$, describe the effects of parallel transport in the manifold, and can be expressed as:

$$\Gamma_{\rho\sigma}^\mu = \frac{1}{2} g^{\mu\nu} \left(\frac{\partial g_{\rho\nu}}{\partial x^\sigma} + \frac{\partial g_{\sigma\nu}}{\partial x^\rho} - \frac{\partial g_{\rho\sigma}}{\partial x^\nu} \right). \quad (1.9)$$

In particular, photons move along null geodesics, which satisfy $ds = g_{\mu\nu} \frac{dx^\mu}{d\lambda} \frac{dx^\nu}{d\lambda} = 0$. Note that so far we have not made use of the hypothesis that General Relativity is valid; the notion of metric is independent of the theory of gravity that we use.

One of the greatest concepts introduced by Einstein in his theory was the fact that the curvature structure of spacetime (embodied in $g_{\mu\nu}$) and the matter-energy density of the contents of the Universe (expressed by the symmetric *stress-energy tensor*, $T_{\mu\nu}$) are intrinsically related. Mathematically, this relationship is written as:

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}\mathcal{R}g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^3}T_{\mu\nu} + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu}, \quad (1.10)$$

These are known as the Einstein Field Equations, and they describe the dynamics of the metric $g_{\mu\nu}$. $R_{\mu\nu}$ is known as the Ricci tensor, \mathcal{R} as the Ricci scalar, and G is Newton's gravitational constant. Both the Ricci tensor and the Ricci scalar contain information about the curvature of spacetime and can be expressed in terms of the metric. In Equation (1.10), we have included a term representing the cosmological constant, Λ . The cosmological constant, initially introduced by Einstein to obtain a static solution out of his equations in accordance with the beliefs of the time, is the simplest explanation to the observed accelerated expansion of the Universe, and it is mathematically equivalent to the energy of the vacuum. The symmetry imposed by the assumptions we have made (Copernican principle plus isotropy) imply that the stress-energy tensor (for the case of the FLRW metric) can be written as that of a homogeneous perfect fluid, determined by its isotropic pressure $p(t)$ and its energy density $\rho(t)$: $T_{\mu\nu} = \text{diag}(\rho, a^{-2}p, a^{-2}p, a^{-2}p)$.

The stress-energy tensor satisfies $\nabla_\mu T^{\mu\nu} = 0$, which is a statement of energy-momentum conservation. The temporal part of the conservation equation gives:

$$\dot{\rho} = -\frac{3\dot{a}}{a}(\rho + p). \quad (1.11)$$

In turn, the temporal component of the Einstein equations plus the definition of $T_{\mu\nu}$ give:

$$\left(\frac{\dot{a}}{a}\right)^2 = \frac{8\pi G}{3}\rho(a) - \frac{\kappa c^2}{a^2} + \frac{\Lambda}{3}, \quad (1.12)$$

which is an equation describing the evolution of the scale factor $a(t)$. Combining Equations (1.11) and (1.12) we obtain a third equation, known as the acceleration equation:

$$\frac{\ddot{a}}{a} = -\frac{4\pi G}{3}(\rho + 3p) + \frac{\Lambda}{3}. \quad (1.13)$$

Equations (1.11), (1.12) and (1.13) are collectively known as the Friedmann Equations. They constitute a system of 2 independent equations for 3 unknowns: $a(t)$, $\rho(t)$ and $p(t)$. The third equation needed is the Equation of State, a relationship between the pressure and the energy density:

$$p(t) = w\rho(t). \quad (1.14)$$

The equation-of-state parameter, w , is generally a function of time. It determines the evolution of the energy density ρ for the case of a perfect fluid.⁵ Solving Equation (1.11), we obtain the evolution of the energy density ρ :

$$\rho \propto \exp \left[3 \int_0^z \frac{1 + w(z')}{1 + z'} dz' \right]. \quad (1.15)$$

For a constant equation-of-state parameter, we have:

$$\rho \propto (1 + z)^{3(1+w)} = a^{-3(1+w)}. \quad (1.16)$$

Non-relativistic matter (baryons⁶ plus cold dark matter) has $w_m = 0$, radiation has $w_r = 1/3$, and the cosmological constant/vacuum energy has $w_\Lambda = -1$. The early Universe, after inflation, was dominated by radiation ($z \gtrsim 3000$), then by matter ($3000 \gtrsim z \gtrsim 0.5$), and just recently ($z \lesssim 0.5$) by dark energy.

The rate of expansion is characterized by the Hubble parameter:

$$H(t) \equiv \frac{\dot{a}}{a}. \quad (1.17)$$

⁵In the more complicated case of a non-perfect, inhomogeneous fluid, the evolution of ρ with time cannot be fully characterized by w .

⁶In cosmology, the term “baryons” is used loosely and includes electrons.

The Hubble parameter at the present time is the Hubble constant, H_0 (Section 1.1.1). Another useful quantity is the density parameter:

$$\Omega = \frac{8\pi G}{3H^2}\rho = \frac{\rho}{\rho_c}, \quad (1.18)$$

where the critical density ρ_c is defined by:

$$\rho_c \equiv \frac{3H^2}{8\pi G}. \quad (1.19)$$

The current value of the critical density is $\rho_{c,0} = 9.22 \times 10^{-27} \text{ kg m}^{-3}$. If we write the first Friedmann equation in terms of the density parameter (see Equation [1.20] below), the critical density determines the value of ρ for which the spatial geometry of the Universe is flat ($\kappa = 0$, $\Omega = 1$). If $\rho < (>)\rho_c$, then $\Omega < (>)1 \Leftrightarrow \kappa < (>)0$ and the Universe is open (closed). Recent measurements of the CMB indicate that we live in a flat ($\Omega = 1$) Universe.

The first Friedmann equation can be written in a more compact form that includes a curvature contribution, if we treat the curvature as if it had an energy density of the form $\rho_\kappa = -3\kappa/8\pi G a^2$ and a density parameter $\Omega_\kappa = -\kappa/H^2 a^2$. Thus,

$$H^2 = \frac{8\pi G}{3} \sum_i \rho_i \iff 1 = \sum_i \Omega_i \iff \Omega_\kappa = 1 - \Omega. \quad (1.20)$$

In the previous equations, the sum is over all the components that make up the total energy density ρ (matter, radiation, vacuum energy, etc.) plus the curvature term previously defined. In terms of the density parameters of the components of the Universe, the first Friedmann equation takes the form:

$$E^2(z) \equiv \frac{H^2}{H_0^2} = \Omega_\kappa(1+z)^2 + \Omega_r(1+z)^4 + \Omega_m(1+z)^3 + \Omega_{de}(1+z)^{3(1+w)}, \quad (1.21)$$

assuming a parameter of state for dark energy that does not vary over time. The deceleration parameter, which measures rate of change of the rate of expansion, is given by:

$$q \equiv -\frac{a\ddot{a}}{\dot{a}^2} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_i \Omega_i(1+3w_i(z)). \quad (1.22)$$

Note that during the matter and radiation dominated eras, w_m and w_r are larger than zero, so $q > 0$ and $\ddot{a} < 0$. However, for the current era, it has been observed that $q < 0$ and $\ddot{a} > 0$. In the second Friedmann equation (Equation [1.12]), a component with negative pressure $p < \rho/3$ has repulsive gravity and can cause the Universe to accelerate, which is one of the defining properties of dark energy.

1.2.2 Cosmological Distances

In cosmology we have to be careful when we talk about the notion of distance, because we live in a curved four-dimensional spacetime that is expanding with time. The most straightforward definition of a distance that we can give is the *proper distance*. The proper distance between two points is equal to the length of the spatial geodesic between them at a fixed value of the scale factor $a(t)$. In terms of the comoving radial position χ :

$$d_p(t) = a(t)\chi. \quad (1.23)$$

The comoving radial distance, χ , to an object at redshift z is the constant distance between two objects that are moving with the Hubble flow, and is given by:

$$\chi(t) = c \int_{t_e}^t \frac{dt'}{a(t')}, \quad (1.24)$$

where t is the present time and t_e the time of emission of photons detected by the observer.

The *conformal time*, η , is given by:

$$\eta = \int_0^t \frac{dt'}{a(t')}. \quad (1.25)$$

An important comoving distance is the distance a photon could have traveled since the Big Bang ($t = 0$):

$$\chi_h \equiv c \int_0^t \frac{dt'}{a(t')}. \quad (1.26)$$

This is called the *particle horizon* or *comoving horizon*. Its importance relies on the fact that no information could have propagated further than χ_h since the

beginning of time, so objects separated by more than χ_h at a particular time are not in causal contact.

Unfortunately, the proper distance does not determine any observable quantities. Therefore, to be able to assign distances to objects in the Universe, we define a set of distances that determine observables such as flux, angular size, etc. These distances are the *luminosity distance*, $d_L(z)$, the *proper motion distance*, $d_M(z)$, and the *angular diameter distance*, $d_A(z)$:

$$d_L(z) \equiv \sqrt{\frac{L}{4\pi F}} = (1+z)f_\kappa[\chi(z)], \quad (1.27)$$

$$d_M(z) \equiv \frac{u}{\dot{\theta}}, \quad (1.28)$$

$$d_A(z) \equiv \frac{R}{\theta}. \quad (1.29)$$

In the equations above, F is the measured energy flux of the object, L the intrinsic luminosity, u the proper transverse velocity, $\dot{\theta}$ the observed angular velocity, R the proper size, and θ its observed angular diameter. Notice how all these means of measuring distance arise from comparing an absolute or intrinsic property of the object (L , u , R) with an apparent one (F , $\dot{\theta}$, θ). They are all simply related by redshift factors:

$$d_L = (1+z)d_M = (1+z)^2d_A. \quad (1.30)$$

Thus, if we measure one of these distances we can derive the other two. In the same way, if we measure two of them independently we can derive the remaining one and check for the consistency of our cosmological model.

In particular, we will be interested in the angular diameter distance, since it is the one mostly used in gravitational lensing theory (Section 1.5.2).

1.3 Formation of Galaxies and the Large Scale Structure of the Universe

Inflation, which states that the early Universe underwent a rapid period of accelerated expansion, was initially proposed to solve the homogeneity and flatness problems of the original formulation of the Big Bang theory. It is also the simplest mechanism to generate the spectrum of density perturbations that eventually evolved to form the large scale structure of the Universe through gravitational instability⁷; quantum fluctuations are amplified to astrophysical scales through the expansion driven by inflation.

Since the density perturbations are small after inflation (as indicated by the amplitude of the the anisotropies in the CMB), their evolution can initially be described by perturbative linear theory. If we assume that matter can be treated as a pressureless, ideal fluid with velocity $\vec{v}(\vec{x}, t)$, then ρ obeys the Continuity Equation and Euler's Equation of fluid dynamics, as well as Poisson's Equation (Schneider, 2006):

- The continuity equation:

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \vec{\nabla}(\rho \cdot \vec{v}) = 0 \quad (1.31)$$

- Euler's equation:

$$\frac{\partial \vec{v}}{\partial t} + (\vec{v} \cdot \vec{\nabla})\vec{v} = -\vec{\nabla}\Phi \quad (1.32)$$

- Poisson's equation:

$$\nabla^2 \Phi = 4\pi G \rho \quad (1.33)$$

The previous equations are expressed in physical or proper coordinates (related to comoving coordinates through the scale factor a). The Newtonian gravitational potential is denoted as Φ , and the density contrast $\delta(\vec{x}, a)$ is defined as $\delta(\vec{x}, a) \equiv (\rho(\vec{x}, a) - \bar{\rho}(a))/\bar{\rho}(a)$ (where $\bar{\rho}$ is the spatially averaged density at a given time t or

⁷These are known as scalar perturbations and lead to the formation of structure. Inflation also produces another type of perturbation, tensor perturbations, that leads to gravitational waves and can leave a signature in the anisotropies of the CMB.

expansion factor $a(t)$). By expressing these equations in comoving coordinates, perturbing them about the homogeneous solution, and linearizing them, we can deduce a differential equation for the linear evolution of δ :

$$\ddot{\delta} + 2\frac{\dot{a}}{a}\dot{\delta} = 4\pi G\rho\delta. \quad (1.34)$$

The solution of this second order differential equation has a decaying (D_2) and a growing (D_1) mode separable solution:

$$\delta(\vec{x}, t) = A(\vec{x})D_1(t) + B(\vec{x})D_2(t). \quad (1.35)$$

D_1 , known as the *growth function*, describes the growth of matter perturbations at late times. We can rewrite Equation (1.34) as an equation for the growth factor (where we have simply set $D_1 = D$, since D_2 will decay with time):

$$\ddot{D} + 2H(z)\dot{D} - \frac{3}{2}\Omega_{m,0}H_0^2(a+z)^3D = 0. \quad (1.36)$$

This growth-redshift relation, along with the (comoving) distance-redshift relation of Equation (1.24), is a probe for dark energy because the rate at which structure grows depends on the contents of the Universe and its evolution history. Moreover, if GR is correct, there is a one-to-one relationship between Equations (1.36) and (1.24), and therefore we are able to test the theory of gravity we assumed in our cosmological model. It has no analytic solution for a general cosmology, although in the case of a flat Universe with a cosmological constant component the solution can be approximated by (Carroll et al., 1992):

$$D(a) \approx \frac{5}{2}a\Omega_m(a) \left[\Omega_m(a)^{4/7} - \Omega_\Lambda(a) + \left(1 + \frac{\Omega_m(a)}{2}\right) \left(1 + \frac{\Omega_\Lambda}{70}\right) \right]^{-1}. \quad (1.37)$$

The density contrast is described as a random field. Let $\delta_{\vec{k}}$ be the Fourier transform of δ . The magnitude of the wave vector k is inversely related to the physical wavelength λ of the perturbations, $k \propto 1/\lambda$. When the phases are uncorrelated, the field δ

is a *Gaussian random field*, which is what inflation theory predicts for the density fluctuations.

The statistical properties of a Gaussian random field are fully specified by its power spectrum, P_δ :

$$(2\pi)^3 \delta^3(\vec{k} - \vec{k}') P_\delta(\vec{k}) \equiv \langle \delta_{\vec{k}} \delta_{\vec{k}'} \rangle, \quad (1.38)$$

where the angular brackets denote an ensemble average, and δ^3 is the 3D Dirac delta function. The Fourier transform of the power spectrum is called the *two-point correlation function*. Weak lensing, through the measurement of cosmic shear (Section 1.5.4), provides a projected measurement of the power spectrum of density fluctuations (see Equation [1.106]). The initial power spectrum, $P_i(\vec{k})$, only depends on the magnitude of the wave vector k due to the isotropy and homogeneity of the Universe. It is usually assumed to take the form of a power law, $P_i(k) \propto k^n$. In the particular case of $n = 1$, we have a scale-invariant or scale-free spectrum (*i.e.*, perturbations of all sizes behave in the same way) known as the Harrison-Zeldovich spectrum. A scale-invariant power spectrum has been supported by observations (and also predicted by inflation), although recent measurements tend to point to a value for n slightly less than 1 (Larson et al., 2011).

After inflation, the Universe was dominated by radiation and the physical scales of density fluctuations grew with the expansion rate as $\lambda \propto a \propto t^{1/2}$. Under gravitational instability, relativistic perturbation theory predicts that density perturbations started to grow linearly with time at all scales. However, during this era dominated by radiation, perturbations smaller than a certain critical size (the *Jeans length*) were prevented from growing due to the radiative pressure counteracting gravity. This manifests as a suppression of power on small scales in the form:

$$P_\delta \propto \frac{P_i(k)}{k^4} \propto k^{n-4}, \quad (1.39)$$

which is known as the *Mészáros effect*. If the initial spectrum is scale invariant, then $P_\delta \propto k$ for $k \ll k_0$ and $P_\delta \propto k^{-3}$ for $k \gg k_0$, where k_0 defines the turning point of the power spectrum. k_0 is set by the time when the densities of radiation and

matter become equal and the Universe started to be dominated by matter (since the matter density function decays slower with time than radiation density as the Universe expands, see Equation [1.16]). It is also the wave vector corresponding to the horizon size at this time of matter-radiation equality, and its value in the standard cosmology is $\approx 0.002 \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ (Larson et al., 2011).

The modification in the power spectrum due to the Mészáros effect is normally encompassed by the *transfer function*:

$$P_\delta(k, z) = T(k, z)^2 P_i(k). \quad (1.40)$$

$T(k, z)$ is a function of the contents of the Universe and is therefore a function of the parameters of the particular cosmological model in hand. The redshift dependence of the transfer function is given by the scale function and the growth factor D :

$$T(k, z) = \frac{D(z)}{D(z=0)} a(z) T(k). \quad (1.41)$$

Bardeen et al. (1986) give a fitting function for the transfer function in terms of the *shape parameter* $\Gamma \equiv \Omega_m h \exp(-2\Omega_{\text{baryons}})$, which determines the shape of the density fluctuation spectrum in the early Universe. The amplitude of the power spectrum of density fluctuations is parameterized in terms of σ_8 , defined as the variance of the density fluctuations in spheres of radius $8h^{-1} \text{ Mpc}$ scattered throughout the Universe. It can be calculated from the power spectrum as:

$$\sigma_8^2 \equiv \int dk \frac{k^2}{2\pi^2} P(k) \left[\frac{3J_1(8k)}{8k} \right]^2 dk, \quad (1.42)$$

where $J_1(x)$ is the first-order spherical Bessel function of the first kind.

After the equality in the densities of radiation and matter, the physical size of fluctuations was $\lambda \propto a \propto t^{2/3}$. There was no radiation pressure present anymore (since now matter dominates the expansion of the Universe) to prevent the growth of densities at all scales. As the Universe expanded, the perturbations grew more and more. Linear theory is no longer valid when $\delta \gg 1$, and large numerical N-body simulations are required to fully take into account the non-linear, high-order

terms. Fitting functions for the non-linear power spectrum were initially developed by Peacock and Dodds (1996) and improved by Smith et al. (2003). Since cosmic shear measurements are sensitive to large matter inhomogeneities, this uncertainty in the non-linear power spectrum constitutes another source of systematic errors (see Section 1.5.5).

1.4 Dark Energy

Dark energy is the term for the causative agent of the observed accelerated expansion of the Universe. The 2011 Nobel Prize in Physics was awarded to the leaders of the two teams who (at the end of the last century) measured an accelerated expansion of the Universe through the study of Type Ia Supernovae (SNe Ia), which are standardizable candles with a known intrinsic luminosity (Riess et al., 1998; Perlmutter et al., 1999).

Dark energy has the following defining properties (Turner, 2001):

- It emits no electromagnetic radiation.
- It has large and negative pressure.
- It does not cluster significantly below horizon scales (*i.e.*, it is approximately homogeneous).

Since its discovery in 1998, several lines of evidence have confirmed this accelerated expansion. Hundreds more SNe Ia light curves have been measured from ground based telescopes that probe the range $z \sim 0.3 - 0.9$ (Supernovae Legacy Survey, SNLS (Astier et al., 2006) and ESSENCE survey (Miknaitis et al., 2007)). Measurements with the Hubble Space Telescope (HST) have allowed the detection of SNe Ia even up to $z \sim 1.8$, providing evidence for earlier deceleration (when matter still dominated over dark energy), addressing earlier concerns that the acceleration was due to dust extinction instead of a new form of energy density (Riess et al., 2007). In addition,

measurements from the CMB (WMAP) have established that the Universe is flat to high accuracy. This means that the matter and energy densities of the components of the Universe must sum to 1. Independent measurements have established that matter (dark and baryonic) make up to about 30% of the total matter-energy density, leaving the remaining 70% as belonging to some unknown energy component. This is in agreement with the results found by the supernovae studies.

Dark energy could be due to a cosmological constant or, equivalently, the energy of the vacuum. The problem with the latter is that while it is physically well motivated, theoretical calculations from quantum field theory provide estimates of the energy density of dark energy that are ~ 60 orders of magnitude off from constraints inferred from current cosmological data. It could also be possible that w changes with time, and dark energy comes from a scalar field (“quintessence”) whose dynamics are similar to those of the field that drove inflation. Another alternative is that GR starts to fail on large scales and that a modification to the theory of gravity of our cosmological model is in order. The first step to learn more about dark energy is to determine the nature of its equation-of-state parameter w . A common parametrization of the variability of w with time is $w(a) = w_0 + w_a(1 - a)$ (Linder, 2003), with w_0 and w_a constants to be determined.

The primary effect of dark energy is on the expansion rate of the Universe, $H(z)$. This, in turn, affects the growth of structure of the Universe (Equation[1.36]) and the redshift-distance relationship (Equation [1.24]). Dark energy is not expected to be dominant at high redshifts, otherwise, the large scale structure formation would have been affected (we would not observe the structure we measure today because dark energy affects the growth of structure through the term $2H\dot{\delta}$ in Equation[1.36]). The most sensitive interval for studying dark energy is $z = 0.2 - 2$, since the Hubble flow at low redshift is not sensitive to the contents of the Universe, and dark energy was less important in the past ($\rho_{de}/\rho_m \propto (1+z)^{3w} \rightarrow 0$ as $z \rightarrow \infty$) (Huterer and Turner, 2001).

The Dark Energy Task Force (DETF) report (Albrecht et al., 2006) has identi-

fied four main techniques to learn more about dark energy. These are: 1) Type Ia supernovae (as standardizable candles, using the luminosity distance d_L), 2) Baryon Acoustic Oscillations, 3) galaxies and galaxy cluster counts (counting the number of dark matter halos in a comoving volume element per unit redshift per unit solid angle, $dV/dz d\Omega = \chi^2(z)/H(z)$, and comparing the measurements to simulations), and 4) weak gravitational lensing (see next Section). Combining these four probes in a cosmological survey, such as DES (Section 1.6) will provide tighter constraints on cosmological parameters and better cross-check for the systematic errors. For instance, the next generation of surveys aim to constrain w at the few percent level and w_a at the 10% level.

1.5 Weak Gravitational Lensing

In Einstein’s GR, the presence of mass-energy affects the curvature of space time. Due to this curvature, photons from background sources bend their trajectories when passing near any mass-energy concentration (the Sun, a black hole, galaxies, clusters of galaxies, etc.). The amount by which the light photons are bent is called the *deflection angle*, and it is directly related to the gravitational potential created by the mass-energy overdensity (also known as the “lens”). In general, the images of the sources are distorted and magnified.

There are different types of gravitational lensing: microlensing, strong lensing and weak lensing. In microlensing, the change in light distribution is on very small angular scales ($10^{-1}\mu$ arcsec) that can’t be resolved, but the change in total flux is still detectable. Microlensing has been used recently in the detection of exoplanets. In strong lensing, multiple images, arcs, or even a single ring (called the “Einstein ring”, see Equation [1.70] below) can form around the lens (Figure 1.2). In weak lensing, on the other hand, the effect on the source’s shape is only of $\sim 1 - 2\%$, and it is impossible to detect it just by studying one galaxy. Thus, a large number of sources is required to statistically detect a coherent elongation in the shapes of the

background sources. Weak lensing is an important tool in cosmological analysis, but it is subject to a large list of systematic errors. In this thesis we are only concerned with weak gravitational lensing, and we will address some of those systematic errors in the context of the Dark Energy Survey (Section 1.6).

Figure 1.2: Example of strong gravitational lensing. The blue horseshoe-shaped arc is the image of a far background galaxy ($z = 2.4$) that has been lensed by a massive foreground galaxy. The alignment between the observer, source and lens is almost perfect, giving rise to this semi-complete version of an Einstein ring (Equation [1.70]). Credit: ESA/HST and NASA. Image taken from <http://www.spacetelescope.org/images/potw1151a/>

1.5.1 The Deflection Angle

We will now spend some time deriving the gravitational lensing deflection angle for a weakly perturbed FLRW metric, since it is an important quantity in gravitational lensing theory. For this purpose, we will model our gravitational sources as dust (a perfect, pressureless fluid), and we will work in the static weak-field limit (allowing, however, the test particles to have any velocity). More precisely, we will assume that $\frac{\Phi}{c^2} \ll 1$ and $\dot{\Phi} = 0$, where Φ can be thought of as the scalar Newtonian potential that obeys Poisson's equation. The perturbed FLRW distance element in the Newtonian gauge for a universe without anisotropic stress can be written as (using natural units in which $c = 1$ and $G = 1$):

$$ds^2 = -(1 + 2\Phi(\vec{x}, t))dt^2 + a^2(t)(1 - 2\Phi(\vec{x}, t))(dx^2 + dy^2 + dz^2). \quad (1.43)$$

Now, if we denote the background FLRW metric as $g_{\mu\nu}^{(0)}$ (which will be used to raise and lower tensor indices, too) and the perturbation as $h_{\mu\nu}$ ($|h_{\mu\nu}| \ll 1$), the perturbed metric can also be written as $g_{\mu\nu} = g_{\mu\nu}^{(0)} + h_{\mu\nu}$. Comparing to Equations (1.5) and (1.43), we have:

$$g_{\mu\nu}^{(0)} = \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & a^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & a^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & a^2 \end{pmatrix}; \quad h_{\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} -2\Phi & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -2\Phi a^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -2\Phi a^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -2\Phi a^2 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (1.44)$$

To derive the deflection angle, $\hat{\alpha}$, we will consider the trajectory of a photon in this geometry. We therefore need to solve the geodesic equation (Equation [1.8]) for a null trajectory, $x^\mu(\lambda)$. This geodesic can also be decomposed into a solution in the background FLRW metric plus a small perturbation:

$$x^\mu = x^{(0)\mu}(\lambda) + x^{(1)\mu}(\lambda). \quad (1.45)$$

We will solve for $x^{(1)\mu}(\lambda)$ by evaluating all the quantities such as integrals and gradients along the background path. The deflection angle will be the amount by which

the wave vector, tangent to the trajectory, rotates along the path. We denote the tangent vectors of $x^{(0)\mu}(\lambda)$ and $x^{(1)\mu}(\lambda)$ as:

$$k^\mu \equiv \frac{dx^{(0)\mu}}{d\lambda}, \quad l^\mu \equiv \frac{dx^{(1)\mu}}{d\lambda}. \quad (1.46)$$

The condition on null-geodesics imposes constraints on the wave vectors. To zeroth order:

$$\begin{aligned} g_{\mu\nu} \frac{dx^{(0)\mu}}{d\lambda} \frac{dx^{(0)\nu}}{d\lambda} &= g_{\mu\nu}^{(0)} k^\mu k^\nu = 0 \\ \Rightarrow a^2 \|\vec{k}\|^2 &= (k^0)^2 \equiv k^2, \\ \vec{k} &= (k^1, k^2, k^3), \end{aligned} \quad (1.47)$$

and to first order:

$$\begin{aligned} g_{\mu\nu} \frac{dx^{(1)\mu}}{d\lambda} \frac{dx^{(1)\nu}}{d\lambda} &= (g_{\mu\nu}^{(0)} + h_{\mu\nu})(k^\mu + l^\mu)(k^\nu + l^\nu) = 0 \\ \Rightarrow 2g_{\mu\nu}^{(0)} k^\mu l^\nu + h_{\mu\nu} k^\mu k^\nu &= 0 \\ \Rightarrow a^2 \vec{k} \cdot \vec{l} - k^0 l^0 &= 2(k^0)^2 \Phi, \\ \vec{l} &= (l^1, l^2, l^3). \end{aligned} \quad (1.48)$$

To solve the geodesic equation, we will proceed again order by order. The solution to the zeroth order part will simply give us the geodesic trajectory in the background FLRW metric, whereas the first order equation is:

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{d^2 x^{(0)\mu}}{d\lambda^2} + \frac{d^2 x^{(1)\mu}}{d\lambda^2} \right) + (\Gamma_{\rho\sigma}^{(0)\mu} + \Gamma_{\rho\sigma}^{(1)\mu}) ((k^\rho + l^\rho)(k^\sigma + l^\sigma)) &= 0 \\ \left(\frac{dk^\mu}{d\lambda} + \Gamma_{\rho\sigma}^{(0)\mu} k^\rho l^\sigma \right) + \frac{dl^\mu}{d\lambda} + \Gamma_{\rho\sigma}^{(1)\mu} k^\rho k^\sigma + 2\Gamma_{\rho\sigma}^{(0)\mu} k^\rho l^\sigma + 2\Gamma_{\rho\sigma}^{(1)\mu} k^\rho l^\sigma &= 0 \\ \Rightarrow \frac{dl^\mu}{d\lambda} &= -\Gamma_{\rho\sigma}^{(1)\mu} k^\rho k^\sigma - 2\Gamma_{\rho\sigma}^{(0)\mu} k^\rho l^\sigma, \end{aligned} \quad (1.49)$$

where we have dropped the first term since it is the solution to the zeroth-order geodesic equation, and the last term, being of second order. The Christoffel symbols, to zeroth and first order, are given by the following expressions:

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma_{\rho\sigma}^{(0)\mu} &= \frac{g^{(0)\mu\lambda}}{2} (\partial_\rho g_{\lambda\sigma}^{(0)} + \partial_\sigma g_{\rho\lambda}^{(0)} - \partial_\lambda g_{\rho\sigma}^{(0)}) \\ \Gamma_{\rho\sigma}^{(1)\mu} &= \frac{g^{(0)\mu\lambda}}{2} (\partial_\rho h_{\lambda\sigma} + \partial_\sigma h_{\rho\lambda} - \partial_\lambda h_{\rho\sigma}) - \frac{h^{\mu\lambda}}{2} (\partial_\rho g_{\lambda\sigma}^{(0)} + \partial_\sigma g_{\rho\lambda}^{(0)} - \partial_\lambda g_{\rho\sigma}^{(0)}). \end{aligned} \quad (1.50)$$

Therefore, the non-zero terms are:

$$\begin{aligned}
\Gamma_{0i}^{(0)i} &= \dot{a}/a = H & \Gamma_{0i}^{(1)i} &= \partial_i \Phi a^{-2} & \Gamma_{22}^{(1)1} &= \Gamma_{33}^{(1)1} = \partial_1 \Phi \\
\Gamma_{ii}^{(0)i} &= a^2 H & \Gamma_{ii}^{(1)i} &= -\partial_i \Phi & \Gamma_{21}^{(1)1} &= -\partial_2 \Phi \\
\Gamma_{0i}^{(1)0} &= \partial_i \Phi & \Gamma_{ii}^{(1)0} &= -\partial_i \Phi \dot{a} a & \Gamma_{31}^{(1)1} &= -\partial_3 \Phi.
\end{aligned}$$

The deflection angle will be given by $\hat{\alpha} = -\Delta \vec{l}/k$ (the minus sign comes from the fact that $\hat{\alpha}$ is measured by an observer looking backwards along the photon path), so we will only need to evaluate the spatial part ($\mu \in [1, 2, 3]$) of Equation (1.49).⁸ We will evaluate the case $\mu = 1$ and then generalize, since the spatial components of the background metric and those of its perturbation are the same (*i.e.*, $g_{11}^{(0)} = g_{22}^{(0)} = g_{33}^{(0)}$ and $h_{11} = h_{22} = h_{33}$)

$$\frac{dl^1}{d\lambda} = -(\partial_1 \Phi ((k^0/a)^2) + k^2 - 2(\vec{\nabla} \Phi \cdot \vec{k})k^1 - 2Hl^1 k^0). \quad (1.51)$$

Generalizing to the three vector components, we have:

$$\frac{d\vec{l}}{d\lambda} = -(2k^2 \vec{\nabla} \Phi - 2(\vec{\nabla} \Phi \cdot \vec{k})\vec{k} - 2Hk^0 \vec{l}). \quad (1.52)$$

We can decompose the gradient of the gravitational field into parallel and perpendicular components:

$$\vec{\nabla} \Phi = \vec{\nabla}_{\parallel} \Phi + \vec{\nabla}_{\perp} \Phi \Rightarrow \vec{\nabla}_{\perp} \Phi = \vec{\nabla} \Phi - k^{-2}(\vec{\nabla} \Phi \cdot \vec{k})\vec{k}. \quad (1.53)$$

Using this in Equation (1.52), we obtain:

$$\frac{d\vec{l}}{d\lambda} = -2k^2 \vec{\nabla}_{\perp} \Phi - 2Hk^0 \vec{l}, \quad (1.54)$$

or in component form:

$$\frac{dl^i}{d\lambda} + 2Hk^0 l^i = -2k^2 \partial_{\perp}^i \Phi. \quad (1.55)$$

⁸The temporal part, $\mu = 0$, can be shown to be equal to $\frac{dl^0}{d\lambda} + (2Hk^0)l^0 = -2k^0(\vec{\nabla} \Phi \cdot \vec{k}) - 6H\Phi(k^0)^2$

To solve these differential equations, we note that each one is of the form $y' + P(x)y = q(x)$, whose solution is (Arfken and Weber, 2001):

$$y(x) = e^{-\int^x P(w)dw} \left(\int^x e^{\int^x P(w)dw} q(u)du + c \right). \quad (1.56)$$

By demanding that $l^i = 0$ for $\Phi = 0$, we have that $c = 0$. By making the identifications $P(\lambda) = 2Hk^0$ and $q(\lambda) = -2k^2 \partial_{\perp}^i \Phi$, and recalling that $k^0 = dx^{(0)0}/d\lambda = dt/d\lambda$, we find that $e^{-\int^x P(w)dw} = a^{-2}$ and $e^{\int^x P(w)dw} = a^2$. This implies that the spatial part of the wave vector l^{μ} is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} l^i &= -2k^2 \int \partial_{\perp}^i \Phi d\lambda \\ \Rightarrow \vec{l} &= -2k^2 \int \vec{\nabla}_{\perp} \Phi d\lambda. \end{aligned} \quad (1.57)$$

Recall that all integrations and gradients are along the background path (this is known as *Born's approximation*). Using Equation (1.57), we finally arrive at the expression of the gravitational lensing deflection angle (expressed in terms of the physical distance travelled by the particle, $s = k\lambda$):

$$\hat{\alpha} = - \left(-2k^2 \int \vec{\nabla}_{\perp} \Phi ds / k \right) \frac{1}{k} \Rightarrow \boxed{\hat{\alpha} = \frac{2}{c^2} \int \vec{\nabla}_{\perp} \Phi ds}. \quad (1.58)$$

In the Equation (1.58) we have reinserted the speed of light. Note that this is the same result as when the background metric is Minkowski's flat metric.

The deflection angle can also be derived using Fermat's Principle⁹, if one assumes that light is traveling through a medium with effective refraction index $n = 1 - 2\Phi/c^2$. Expressing Fermat's Principle in terms of the usual Euler-Lagrange equations of variational calculus, the deflection angle can be proven to be the integral along the light path of the gradient of n perpendicular to the light path:

$$\hat{\alpha} = - \int \vec{\nabla}_{\perp} n ds = \frac{2}{c^2} \int \vec{\nabla}_{\perp} \Phi ds, \quad (1.59)$$

⁹“The optical length (the physical length times the index of refraction) of the path taken by light between two fixed points is an extremum.”

which is the same result as obtained before. Since $n > 1$, the speed of light is reduced in the spacetime surrounding the lens, giving rise to a gravitational time delay known as Shapiro delay (Shapiro 1964):

$$\Delta t = - \int_o^s \frac{2}{c^3} \Phi ds, \quad (1.60)$$

where the integral is over the light path from the observer to the source.

In the case of a point mass, where the gravitational potential is given by $\Phi(r) = -GM/r$ and denoting the distance of closest approach to the lens (the “impact parameter”) by b , the deflection angle is (only the radial component of the gradient contributes to the integral):

$$\hat{\alpha} = \frac{2}{c^2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} ds \frac{GMb}{(b^2 + s^2)^{3/2}} = \frac{4GM}{c^2 b}. \quad (1.61)$$

We note that for weak gravitational lensing, the light deflection generally occurs in a small region compared to the distance between the source and the deflector (lens) and between the deflector and the observer. This allows us to project the mass distribution of the lens, ρ , to a 2D sheet (the “lens plane”) perpendicular to the line of sight, which is characterized by its surface-mass density:

$$\Sigma(\vec{\xi}) = \int \rho(\vec{\xi}, s) ds, \quad (1.62)$$

where $\vec{\xi}$ is a vector in the lens plane. This is known as the *thin lens approximation*. The deflection angle at point $\vec{\xi}$ is given in this case by the sum of all the deflections caused by the mass elements of the plane:

$$\hat{\alpha} = \frac{4G}{c^2} \int \frac{(\vec{\xi} - \vec{\xi}') \Sigma(\vec{\xi}')}{|\vec{\xi} - \vec{\xi}'|^2} d^2 \xi'^2. \quad (1.63)$$

In the case of a circularly symmetric lens, the deflection angle vector always points towards the center of the lens, and its magnitude is given by:

$$\hat{\alpha}(\xi) = \frac{4GM(\xi)}{c^2 \xi}, \quad (1.64)$$

where ξ is the distance measured from the center, and the mass enclosed within a radius ξ is given by $M(\xi) = 2\pi \int_0^\xi \Sigma(\xi') \xi' d\xi'$.

1.5.2 The Lens Equation and the Lensing Potential

The basic geometry of gravitational lensing is shown in Figure 1.3. The source is located at point S , and its image I is observed at an angle $\hat{\alpha}$ by an observer at O . If the lens did not exist, the image of the source would be found at position $\vec{\beta}$. $\vec{\theta}$ is the angular distance from the optical axis to the image. The distances between the object and the source, the object and the deflector (lens), and the deflector and the source are denoted by D_s , D_d , and D_{ds} , respectively. These are all angular diameter distances (Equation 1.30), so, by their definitions and given that the angles in Figure 1.3 are small we can use the Euclidean relationship for the arc length s subtended by an angle θ , $s = r\theta$ (although, in general, $D_{ds} \neq D_s - D_d$). Applying this to the distance between I and S in Figure 1.3, we obtain:

$$\vec{\beta} = \vec{\theta} - \frac{D_{ds}}{D_s} \hat{\alpha} (D_d \vec{\theta}) = \vec{\theta} - \vec{\alpha}(\vec{\theta}), \quad (1.65)$$

where we have defined the reduced angle $\vec{\alpha}$ in the second equality. This relation is known as the *lens equation*. It is non-linear in general and can have multiple solutions for $\vec{\theta}$, potentially creating multiple images in the strong-lensing regime.

Note that the reduced angle can be written as $\vec{\alpha} = \nabla_{\perp} \left(\frac{2D_{ds}}{D_s c^2} \int \Phi ds \right)$. Therefore, $(\vec{\theta} - \vec{\beta})$ can be written as the gradient of a potential, $\vec{\nabla}_{\theta} \psi$, where $\vec{\nabla}_{\theta} = D_d \vec{\nabla}_{\perp}$ is the angular gradient. This potential is known as the *lensing potential*, and it is a scaled projection of the 3D Newtonian potential:

$$\psi(\vec{\theta}) = \frac{2D_{ds}}{D_d D_s} \int \Phi(D_d \vec{\theta}, s) ds. \quad (1.66)$$

We can then write the lens equation as:

$$\vec{\nabla}_{\theta} \left(\frac{1}{2} (\vec{\theta} - \vec{\beta})^2 - \psi \right) = 0. \quad (1.67)$$

This implies that images will be formed at the stationary points of the surface described by the term in brackets. This surface is called the *time delay surface*:

$$t(\vec{\theta}, \vec{\beta}) = \frac{1 + z_d}{c} \frac{D_d D_s}{D_{ds}} \left(\frac{1}{2} (\vec{\theta} - \vec{\beta})^2 - \psi \right). \quad (1.68)$$

Figure 1.3: Schematic of the deflection of light in gravitational lensing. Assuming the thin lens approximation, the deflector mass lies on a plane perpendicular to the observer O at an angular diameter distance D_d . The source is originally located at point S which is at a distance D_{ds} from the lens and D_s from the source. If there were no lens, the source would be observed at location β . However, due to the effect of gravitational lensing, a photon from the source is deflected by an amount $\hat{\alpha}$, causing the image to appear at location θ . Credit: Narayan and Bartelmann (1996)

The first term is just the geometrical time delay that arises due to the difference in path length between a lensed ray of light and the straight path that would result in the absence of the lens. The second term is the gravitational Shapiro delay introduced above (Equation [1.60]). If there were no lens, only a single stationary point would be produced (that of the parabola defined by the first term). Subsequent stationary points due to the second term come in pairs, so the number of images formed has to be odd. This is known as the *Odd Number Theorem* (Schneider et al., 1992). Note also that the angular diameter distances of Equation (1.68) depend on the Hubble constant. Thus, if we have a model for the lensing potential ψ , we can determine this cosmological parameter by measuring the time delay of different images of the same source (Refsdal, 1964).

For a point mass, the lens equation takes the form (setting ξ from Equation [1.62] to $D_d\theta$):

$$\beta = \theta - \frac{D_{ds}}{D_d D_s} \frac{4GM}{c^2 \theta}. \quad (1.69)$$

In the special case where the source and the lens are aligned ($\beta = 0$), the image takes the form of a ring whose angular radius is called the Einstein radius:

$$\theta_E = \sqrt{\frac{4GM}{c^2} \frac{D_{ds}}{D_d D_s}}. \quad (1.70)$$

1.5.3 Weak lensing observables: convergence and shear

The Laplacian of the lensing potential is proportional to the surface-mass density of the lens:

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla_{\theta}^2 \psi &= \frac{2}{c^2} \frac{D_{ds} D_d}{D_s} \int \left(\nabla^2 - \frac{\partial^2}{\partial s^2} \right) \Phi \, ds \\ &= \frac{D_{ds} D_d}{D_s} \frac{8\pi G}{c^2} \int \rho \, ds \\ &= \frac{D_{ds} D_d}{D_s} \frac{8\pi G \Sigma (D_d \vec{\theta})}{c^2} \equiv \frac{2\Sigma (D_d \vec{\theta})}{\Sigma_c} \equiv 2\kappa, \end{aligned} \quad (1.71)$$

where we have assumed that the derivative of the potential vanishes far away from the lens and that the gravitational Poisson's equation holds ($\nabla^2 \Phi = 4\pi G \rho$). The

critical surface density is defined as:

$$\Sigma_c \equiv \frac{c^2 D_s}{4\pi G D_{ds} D_d}. \quad (1.72)$$

The term κ is known as the *convergence*. It can be viewed as a measure of the integrated mass density of the lens, and it describes the magnification of the image due to the focusing of light rays caused by the lens. It can be written in terms of the critical surface density as:

$$\kappa(\vec{\theta}) = \frac{\Sigma(D_d \vec{\theta})}{\Sigma_{cr}}. \quad (1.73)$$

Since it satisfies the 2D Poisson equation (Equation [1.71]), the lensing potential can be written as:

$$\psi(\vec{\theta}) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int \kappa(\vec{\theta}') \ln |\vec{\theta} - \vec{\theta}'| d^2 \theta', \quad (1.74)$$

and so the reduced angle takes the form:

$$\vec{\alpha}(\vec{\theta}) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int d^2 \theta' \frac{(\vec{\theta} - \vec{\theta}') \kappa(\vec{\theta}')}{|\vec{\theta} - \vec{\theta}'|^2}. \quad (1.75)$$

The effect of weak gravitational lensing can be expressed locally as a linear map of the surface brightness distribution of the source:

$$I^{\text{obs}}(\theta_i) = I^{\text{s}}(A_{ij} \theta_j). \quad (1.76)$$

This map is specified by the lens equation introduced above, and can be characterized by its Jacobian matrix A :

$$A_{ij} = \frac{\partial \beta_i}{\partial \theta_j} = \delta_{ij} - \frac{\partial \alpha_i}{\partial \theta_j} = \delta_{ij} - \psi_{,ij} \Rightarrow -\psi_{,ij} = A_{ij} - \delta_{ij}, \quad (1.77)$$

where a subscript comma followed by a subscript index denotes partial differentiation, and $\psi_{,ij}$ is referred as the *distortion tensor*. The matrix A encodes the local properties of the lensing map. Note that by subtracting the identity δ_{ij} from A_{ij} we are left with the part that describes the distortion of the light path due to inhomogeneities (since in the absence of these, $\vec{\beta} = \vec{\theta}$, and A turns into the identity matrix). The inverse of A is called *the magnification tensor*:

$$M \equiv A^{-1}. \quad (1.78)$$

The determinant of M , $\det M \equiv \mu$, is called *magnification*. The magnification describes how the original area element changes under the lensing map, and thus can be written as the ratio of the solid angle $\delta^2\theta$ to $\delta^2\beta$.

Defining the complex shear $\gamma = \gamma_1 + i\gamma_2$ in terms of the lensing potential as:

$$\begin{aligned}\gamma_1 &\equiv \frac{1}{2}(\partial_1\partial_1\psi - \partial_2\partial_2\psi) \\ \gamma_2 &\equiv \partial_1\partial_2\psi,\end{aligned}\tag{1.79}$$

and writing the convergence as $\kappa = (1/2)(\partial_1\partial_1\psi + \partial_2\partial_2\psi)$ (Equation [1.71]), we can express the Jacobian matrix A as:

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} 1 - \kappa & 0 \\ 0 & 1 - \kappa \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} -\gamma_1 & \gamma_2 \\ \gamma_2 & \gamma_1 \end{pmatrix} = (1 - \kappa) \begin{pmatrix} 1 - g_1 & -g_2 \\ -g_2 & 1 + g_1 \end{pmatrix},\tag{1.80}$$

where the last equality defined the *reduced shear* g_i as $g_i \equiv \gamma_i/(1 - \kappa)$. This illustrates how the anisotropic behavior of the Jacobian A is given by g and not γ , implying that measurements of shapes can only determine the former and not the latter. Since the magnification is the determinant of $M = A^{-1}$, we have:

$$\mu = \frac{1}{(1 - \kappa^2) - \gamma^2}.\tag{1.81}$$

A circular image of unit radius turns into an ellipse of axis $a = (1 - \kappa - \gamma)^{-1}$ and $b = (1 - \kappa + \gamma)^{-1}$ under the effect of weak lensing.

Shear and convergence in Fourier space

The relationship between shear and convergence is more apparent in Fourier space¹⁰. Taking first the Fourier transform of the lensing potential:

$$\psi(\vec{\theta}) = \int \frac{d\ell^2}{(2\pi)^2} \tilde{\psi}(\vec{\ell}) e^{-i\vec{\ell}\cdot\vec{\theta}}\tag{1.82}$$

$$\Rightarrow \tilde{\psi}(\vec{\ell}) = \int d^2\psi(\vec{\theta}) e^{i\vec{\ell}\cdot\vec{\theta}}.\tag{1.83}$$

¹⁰Fourier decomposition in this case implicitly assumes the flat-sky approximation. A more complete treatment would be done in terms of spherical harmonics.

Thus (remembering that the derivate operator $\vec{\nabla}$ can be replaced by the factor $-i\vec{\ell}$ in Fourier space):

$$\begin{aligned}
2\tilde{\kappa}(\vec{\ell}) &= -\ell^2\tilde{\psi}(\vec{\ell}) \\
2\tilde{\gamma}(\vec{\ell}) &= -((\ell_1^2 - \ell_2^2) + 2i\ell_1\ell_2)\tilde{\psi}(\vec{\ell}) \\
&= -\ell^2\tilde{\psi}(\vec{\ell})e^{2i\beta} = 2\tilde{\kappa}(\vec{\ell})e^{2i\beta},
\end{aligned}
\tag{1.84}$$

where β is the polar angle of $\vec{\ell}$. These relations are fundamental when reconstructing the surface mass distribution of a cluster (Kaiser and Squires, 1993). They also can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{“E”} &\equiv \cos(2\beta)\tilde{\gamma}_1 + \sin(2\beta)\tilde{\gamma}_2 \\
\text{“B”} &\equiv -\sin(2\beta)\tilde{\gamma}_1 + \cos(2\beta)\tilde{\gamma}_2.
\end{aligned}$$

This allows us to see that any shear pattern can be decomposed into “E” and “B” modes (analogous to the electromagnetic field). Since the weak lensing shear arises from a potential, we expect the lensing field to be curl-free, *i.e.*, we expect the “B” mode to vanish. Therefore, the presence of any “B” mode indicates that systematic errors remain.

Shapes as estimators of shear

In weak lensing measurements, we usually have the task of constructing a statistical estimator of the shear field given a set of measured galaxy shapes and their measurement errors. The magnification is an observable too, but it is more difficult to detect and therefore, the majority of weak lensing experiments focus on measuring the shear.

The shapes are usually defined in terms of the weighted second moments of the

measured surface brightness :

$$\begin{aligned}
I_{ij} &\equiv \int d^2\theta w(\vec{\theta}) I(\vec{\theta}) \theta_i \theta_j \\
e_1 &\equiv \frac{I_{11} - I_{22}}{I_{11} + I_{22}} \\
e_2 &\equiv \frac{2I_{12}}{I_{11} + I_{22}} \\
r &\equiv I_{11} + I_{22}.
\end{aligned} \tag{1.85}$$

For an image with circular isophotes, $I_{11} = I_{22}$ and $I_{12} = 0$. The complex ellipticities are defined as:

$$\chi \equiv \frac{I_{11} - I_{22} + 2iI_{12}}{I_{11} + I_{22}} \tag{1.86}$$

$$\epsilon \equiv \frac{I_{11} - I_{22} + 2iI_{12}}{I_{11} + I_{22} + 2\sqrt{I_{11}I_{22} - I_{12}^2}}. \tag{1.87}$$

For an image with elliptical isophotes with axes a and b , and if the weight w matches the shape of the object (or if it equals unity), we have:

$$\chi = \frac{1 - q^2}{1 + q^2} e^{2i\phi} = \frac{a^2 - b^2}{a^2 + b^2} e^{2i\phi} \tag{1.88}$$

$$\epsilon = \frac{1 - q}{1 + q} e^{2i\phi} = \frac{a - b}{a + b} e^{2i\phi}, \tag{1.89}$$

where $q \equiv \frac{b}{a}$ and the position angle is ϕ .

We can define the shape of an object in different ways. Following the convention of Bernstein and Jarvis (2002), we define the shape of an object as the inverse shear that is necessary to make the object look circular under a particular definition of roundness. In this way, the shear and the shape belong to the same non-Euclidean manifold, and the action of a shear on a shape is well-defined mathematically. A particular parameterization of shear that will be used in this thesis is the *distortion* δ , defined as:

$$\delta = \frac{1 - q^2}{1 + q^2} \tag{1.90}$$

It should be noted that, in the weak lensing limit, $\delta \ll 1$. On the other hand, the shapes of galaxies can be as large as ~ 1 . Also, in the weak lensing limit, $\delta \approx 2g \approx 2\gamma$.

If a distortion $\vec{\delta} = (\delta_1, \delta_2)$ acts on an object with intrinsic ellipticity $\vec{e} = (e_1, e_2)$, then the resulting shape $\vec{e}' = (e'_1, e'_2)$ is given by (Miralda-Escude, 1991):

$$\begin{aligned} e'_1 &= \frac{e_1 + \delta_1 + (\delta_2/\delta^2)(e_2\delta_1 - e_1\delta_2)(1 - \sqrt{1 - \delta^2})}{1 + \vec{\delta} \cdot \vec{e}} \\ e'_2 &= \frac{e_2 + \delta_2 + (\delta_1/\delta^2)(e_1\delta_2 - e_2\delta_1)(1 - \sqrt{1 - \delta^2})}{1 + \vec{\delta} \cdot \vec{e}}. \end{aligned} \quad (1.91)$$

Note that this shear addition operation is non-commutative. With this formula in hand, we can study the effect of a uniform distortion $\delta \ll 1$ applied to an ensemble of measured galaxy shapes $\{\vec{e}_i\}$. To first order in δ , Equations (1.91) read:

$$\begin{aligned} e'_1 &\approx e_1 + (1 - e_1^2)\delta_1 - e_1e_2\delta_2 \\ e'_2 &\approx e_2 + (1 - e_2^2)\delta_2 - e_1e_2\delta_1. \end{aligned} \quad (1.92)$$

Taking the ensemble average over the measured shapes, and noticing that $\langle e_1 \rangle = \langle e_2 \rangle = \langle e_1e_2 \rangle = 0$ due to the isotropy of the Universe, we have:

$$(\langle e'_1 \rangle, \langle e'_2 \rangle) = ((1 - \langle e_1^2 \rangle)\delta_1, (1 - \langle e_2^2 \rangle)\delta_2) \quad (1.93)$$

The term $\langle e_1^2 \rangle = \langle e_2^2 \rangle \equiv \sigma_{\text{SN}}$ is called the *shape noise*, and it is the variance of the intrinsic shapes of the galaxies. It is typically of the order of ~ 0.3 , whereas the weak lensing signal δ is of the order of 0.02. Hence, a large number of galaxies is needed in weak gravitational lensing to beat down the intrinsic shape noise of galaxies. Notice too that, in the weak lensing limit, the average of the observed shapes is proportional to the shear $\vec{\delta}$. The constant of proportionality is called *responsivity*, and in this case is given by $\mathcal{R} = 1 - \sigma_{\text{SN}}^2$.

In practice, the estimate of a distortion from a set of measured shapes is (Section 5 of Bernstein and Jarvis (2002)):

$$\hat{\delta} = \frac{1}{\mathcal{R}} \frac{\sum \vec{e}}{\sum w} \quad (1.94)$$

$$\text{Var}(\hat{\delta}_i) = \frac{1}{\mathcal{R}^2} \frac{\sum w^2 e_i^2}{\sum w^2} \quad (1.95)$$

$$\mathcal{R} = \frac{\sum[w(1 - k_0 - k_1 e^2/2) + (e/2)(dw/de)(1 - k_0 - k_1 e^2)]}{\sum w} \quad (1.96)$$

$$k_0 = (1 - f)\sigma_{\text{SN}}, \quad k_1 = f^2 \quad (1.97)$$

$$f = \frac{\sigma_{\text{SN}}^2}{\sigma_{\text{SN}}^2 + \sigma_e^2} \quad (1.98)$$

It should be noted that Equation (1.96) is an approximation (it assumes that the measurement error of the galaxies ellipticities only depends on the applied distortion δ to first order), and Equations (1.97) and (1.98) assume that the intrinsic distribution of galaxy ellipticities is Gaussian. The optimal weight w can be approximated by $w = \sqrt{e^2 + 2.25\sigma_e^2}$, where σ_e is the shape uncertainty in each component.¹¹

The main steps of the shear measurement problem are illustrated in Figure 1.4. The image of each galaxy, whose intrinsic ellipticity e_g is unknown, is sheared by the matter inhomogeneities. This is the cosmological shear's signal we are interested in recovering. For ground-based observations, the photons pass through the atmosphere and telescope optics. The image is therefore convolved by a kernel, also known as the *Point Spread Function* (PSF), with ellipticities $e_{1\star}$ and $e_{2\star}$. The PSF makes the galaxies look rounder, effectively erasing the shear signal. On the other hand, any anisotropy in the PSF can make the galaxies look more elongated in the direction of the anisotropy, effectively adding a spurious shear signal to the cosmological shear. The light from the galaxy then hits the square pixels of the detector, and then Poisson noise due to the finite number of photons arriving to the detector and Gaussian noise from the detector are added to the image. Our task is to deconvolve the effect of the PSF from the galaxy as best as possible to recover the shear. In order to do this, we need to create a functional model of the PSF along the field of view of each image. Since the physical sizes of stars are much smaller than the large distances that separate them from us, they can be considered as being point-like sources, and their images on the detectors provide a sample of the PSF. Hence, we can use measurements of the shapes of the stars to correct for the effect of the PSF on galaxies.

¹¹Strictly speaking, an optimal w requires knowledge of the intrinsic distribution of galaxies, see Bernstein and Jarvis (2002).

We can get an idea of how the error in the determination of the PSF during deconvolution can propagate into the derived properties of the pre-seeing (lensed) galaxy by looking at the case where the sizes and shapes of the PSF and galaxies are expressed in terms of second moments (Equations [1.85]).

The Forward Process.

Galaxies: Intrinsic galaxy shapes to measured image:

Stars: Point sources to star images:

Figure 1.4: Forward process in shear measurements. An original galaxy with an intrinsic shape is lensed, blurred, pixelated, and then made noisy (upper panels). Stars can be considered point-like sources and undergo the same process (without being sheared). Our task is to recover the (reduced) shear g using only the information in the last image of each row. Image taken from Bridle et al. (2009)

In this case, the unweighted second moments of the observed galaxy are simply the sum of those of the PSF and the pre-seeing galaxy. Thus, if we have a PSF with ellipticity e_\star and radius r_\star convolved with a galaxy of shape e_g and size r_g , the ellipticity of the observed galaxy is given by (for simplicity we only consider the first

ellipticity component):

$$\begin{aligned}
e_o &= \frac{I_{11} - I_{22}}{I_{11} + I_{22}} \\
&= \frac{(1 + e_\star)r_\star^2 + (1 + e_g)r_g^2 - (1 - e_\star)r_\star^2 - (1 - e_g)r_g^2}{(1 + e_\star)r_\star^2 + (1 + e_g)r_g^2 + (1 - e_\star)r_\star^2 + (1 - e_g)r_g^2} \\
&= \frac{e_\star r_\star^2 + e_g r_g^2}{r_\star^2 + r_g^2},
\end{aligned} \tag{1.99}$$

and its observed size is:

$$r_o^2 = r_\star^2 + r_g^2 \tag{1.100}$$

Estimating the size of the intrinsic galaxy as $\hat{r}_g^2 = r_o^2 - r_\star^2$, we can write an estimator of its pre-seeing shape as:

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{e}_g &= \left(e_o - e_\star \frac{r_\star^2}{r_o^2} \right) \frac{r_o^2}{r_o^2 - r_\star^2} \\
&= e_o \frac{r_o^2}{r_o^2 - r_\star^2} - e_\star \frac{r_\star^2}{r_o^2 - r_\star^2} \\
&= e_o \frac{\hat{r}_g^2 + r_\star^2}{\hat{r}_g^2} - e_\star \frac{r_\star^2}{\hat{r}_g^2}.
\end{aligned} \tag{1.101}$$

The first term of the right hand side (r.h.s) of this equation can be associated with the dilution effect caused by the PSF. This effect represents a modulation of the signal that can cause a calibration error in the shear determination. In the weak lensing literature, this calibration or multiplicative error is usually denoted as m , and any additive error as c ($\gamma^{\text{est}} - \gamma^{\text{true}} = m\gamma^{\text{true}} + c$, see Section 1.5.5 below). A fractional change in that term will contribute to the multiplicative term of our error parameterization. In the same way, the second term can be linked to the c parameter, given that it depends explicitly on the PSF ellipticity. Thus, it represents an anisotropy that breaks the intrinsic symmetry in the orientation of galaxies, and therefore can mimic a lensing signal. In Section 2.2.2 we will use these two terms from the r.h.s. of Equation (1.101) to quantify the accuracy that we must reach in the recovery of the parameters of our PSF models in order to comply with the DES requirements on m and c .

1.5.4 Cosmic Shear

Weak gravitational lensing constitutes a method to measure directly the distribution of dark matter and the value of the cosmological parameters of the Λ CDM model, and to know more about the nature of dark energy through the expansion history and the growth of structures of the Universe. This is accomplished through the careful measurement of the distortions that lensing induces as photons encounter inhomogeneities due to the large-scale structure (LSS). This is termed *cosmic shear*, and was first measured by four groups independently in 2000 (Bacon et al. (2000), Kaiser et al. (2000), Witmman et al. (2000), Van Waerbeke et al. (2000)). Cosmic shear, unlike other methods that trace light distribution, measures mass directly and thus has the power to constrain cosmological parameters. We will see that for sources at a single redshift z_s , the lensing distortion by the 3D mass-energy distribution can be considered due to a single lens with potential ψ and effective convergence, κ_{eff} . We begin by writing Poisson's Equation in comoving coordinates:

$$\nabla^2\Phi = \frac{3H_0^2\Omega_m}{2a}\delta. \quad (1.102)$$

Applying this relationship to Equation (1.71), we obtain:

$$\kappa_{\text{eff}}(\vec{\theta}, \chi) = \frac{3H_0^2\Omega_m}{2c^2} \int_0^\chi d\chi' \frac{d_A(\chi)d_A(\chi - \chi')}{d_A(\chi)} \frac{\delta(d_A(\chi')\vec{\theta}, \chi')}{a(\chi')}. \quad (1.103)$$

In real observations the sources will not be at a single redshift but will be distributed according to a distribution with $p_z(z)dz = p_\chi(\chi)d\chi$. Therefore, Equation (1.103) becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} \kappa_{\text{eff}}(\vec{\theta}) &= \int d\chi p_\chi(\chi) \kappa_{\text{eff}}(\vec{\theta}, \chi) \\ &= \frac{3H_0^2\Omega_m}{2c^2} \int_0^{\chi_h} d\chi g(\chi) d_A(\chi) \frac{\delta(d_A(\chi)\vec{\theta}, \chi)}{a(\chi)}, \end{aligned} \quad (1.104)$$

where χ_h is the comoving distance to the horizon (Section 1.30), and $g(\chi)$ is

$$g(\chi) = \int_\chi^{\chi_h} d\chi' p_\chi(\chi') \frac{d_A(\chi' - \chi)}{d_A(\chi')}. \quad (1.105)$$

For a flat Universe, $d_A(\chi) = \chi$.

The cosmic shear field at a point in the sky is estimated by locally averaging the shapes of large numbers of distant galaxies. The principal cosmic shear observable is the shear-shear correlation function. Its Fourier transform is called the shear power spectrum, $P^{\kappa\kappa}(\ell)$. Using the Limber Equation in Fourier space (Kaiser (1992)), this relationship is given by:

$$P^{\kappa\kappa}(\ell) = P^{\gamma\gamma}(\ell) = \frac{9H_0^2\Omega_m^2}{4c^2} \int_0^{\chi_h} d\chi \frac{g^2(\chi)}{a^2(\chi)} P_\delta \left(\frac{\ell}{d_A(\chi)}, \chi(z) \right), \quad (1.106)$$

where ℓ is the multipole variable conjugate of the angular variable θ . In the previous equation we have denoted κ_{eff} simply as κ , using the fact that the shear power spectrum and the (effective) convergence power spectrum are the same (because they only differ by a complex phase, see Equation [1.84]).

We can also measure angular cross-correlations between foreground galaxy positions and source galaxy shear. These statistics are called galaxy-shear correlations. We can also express these cross- power spectra as projections of the corresponding three-dimensional power spectra, and therefore the shear-shear, galaxy-shear, and galaxy-angular power spectra can all be summarized as (Hu and Jain, 2004):

$$P_\ell^{x_i x_j} = \int dz \frac{H^2(z)}{d_A^2} W_i(z) W_j(z) P^{f_i f_j}(k = \ell/d_A; z), \quad (1.107)$$

where $i, j \in [1, 2]$, x_1 and x_2 denote the two-dimensional angular galaxy and shear fields (g and γ , respectively), and f_1 and f_2 are the 3D galaxy (g) and mass (δ) density fluctuations at redshift z . For instance, $P^{\gamma\gamma}$ and $P^{g\gamma}$ would denote the 2D shear-shear and galaxy-shear correlation functions, and P^{gg} and $P^{\delta\delta}$ would represent the 3D galaxy and density power spectrum, respectively (which, in the simplest case, are related by the so-called *bias parameter* b). $W_i(z)$ and $W_j(z)$ are weight functions that have information about the redshift distribution and the lensing efficiency (using the notation in Hu and Jain (2004)):

$$W(z) = \frac{3}{2} \Omega_m \frac{H_0^2}{H} \frac{d_A(\chi)}{a} \int_z^\infty dz' \frac{d_A(\chi' - \chi)}{d_A(\chi')} w_g(z'), \quad (1.108)$$

with the normalized redshift distribution function $w_g(z) = d_A^2 \bar{n}_V / H \bar{n}_A (\int w_g(z) dz = 1)$. In turn, the 3D number density is \bar{n}_V and the angular number density (sr^{-1}) is given by $\bar{n}_A = \int dz (d_A^2 / H) \bar{n}_V$.

These correlation functions are measured in source-galaxy redshift bins, implying that the photons from galaxies at low z will have only been lensed by nearby matter inhomogeneities, while those at high z will have felt the effect of a wider range of mass fluctuations along the line of sight. This technique is referred to as “cosmic shear tomography” (Hu, 2002), and this makes cosmic shear sensitive to the growth of structure (Section 1.3), which is a way to probe dark energy. The correlation functions are also sensitive to the dark energy density and equation of state through geometrical factors such as the Hubble parameter, the angular diameter distance and the weight functions. Cosmic tomography also makes it possible to map the tridimensional dark matter distribution of the Universe.

In the case of the shear-shear power spectrum¹², the statistical uncertainty is given by (Kaiser, 1992):

$$\Delta P_l^{\gamma\gamma} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{(2l+1)f_{sky}}} \left[P_l^{\gamma\gamma} + \frac{\sigma^2(\gamma_i)}{n_{eff}} \right], \quad (1.109)$$

where f_{sky} is the fraction of sky area covered by the survey, $\sigma^2(\gamma_i)$ is the variance in a single component of the shear, and n_{eff} is the effective number density per steradian of galaxies with well-measured shapes. The first term in brackets represents the sample variance of the mass distribution, and the second, shot-noise term results from both the variance in galaxy ellipticities (shape noise) and from shape-measurement errors due to noise in the images.

Cosmic shear is becoming a central tool in current observational cosmology. It directly measures the matter distribution at low redshifts ($z \lesssim 1$) and probes the non-linear matter power spectrum, constituting an excellent complement to the CMB measurements (where $z \approx 1000$ and the spectrum is linear). Moreover, the use of these two techniques helps to place constraints on cosmological parameters and

¹²In general, this formula is valid for any Gaussian field.

lift degeneracies (Hu and Tegmark, 1999). Cosmic shear also provides a method of finding cluster-scale matter concentrations through the identifications of peaks in the shear/convergence fields. Finally, since the dark energy started to dominate the expansion of the Universe recently, cosmic shear, along with supernovae observations, provides a way to empirically measure its properties.

1.5.5 List of Systematic Effects in Weak Lensing and Cosmic Shear

Weak gravitational lensing and, in particular, cosmic shear by the LSS are powerful tools for observational cosmology. However, the cosmic shear signal is on the order of 1 – 2% of the intrinsic ellipticities of the galaxies, and its measurement is subject to numerous observational and theoretical systematic errors that must be overcome. Some of these errors are (Hoekstra and Jain, 2008):

- Knowledge of PSF and distortion variations: an accurate model of the PSF is necessary to correct for the circularizing effect of the PSF and the detection bias induced by its anisotropy (galaxies whose shape matches that of the PSF tend to be more easily detected). Also, optical effects such as distortions in the telescope (*e.g.*, pincushion/barrel distortion), astigmatism, coma, etc. must be adequately modeled.
- Correction of PSF and shear calibration: deconvolution of the PSF is one of the most difficult steps in measuring gravitational shear. The PSF intrinsic ellipticity can be $\sim 10\%$ of the galaxy ellipticity, whereas the shear signal $\sim 1\%$. It is also necessary to interpolate the PSF function to the galaxy locations, using only the limited sampling of the PSF provided by the stars.
- Intrinsic alignments: physically close galaxies can systematically align due to gravitational interactions, masquerading as the effect of the shear field.

- Errors in photometric redshifts: cosmic tomography depends on an accurate knowledge of the source’s redshift distribution. The large amount of galaxies demanded by weak lensing makes it unpractical to resort to obtain spectra for all the galaxies, and therefore photometric redshifts must be used. The former, however, are subject to more uncertainties that must be controlled.
- Non-linear power spectrum uncertainties (Section 1.3)

Figure 1.5: Statistical error degradation in cosmological parameter as due to shear calibration errors. Image taken from Huterer et al. (2006).

The estimated shear can generally be parameterized in terms of multiplicative and additive errors as (Heymans et al., 2006):

$$\gamma - \gamma^{\text{true}} = m\gamma^{\text{true}} + c. \quad (1.110)$$

Controlling the multiplicative (m) and additive (c) errors is a fundamental task for reaching the full potential of weak lensing (Albrecht et al., 2006). Figure 1.5 shows the degradation from pure statistical errors that cosmological parameters such as Ω_m , σ_8 , w_0 , and w_a can experience due to the presence of significant multiplicative errors

in the shear. For instance, a multiplicative error of 1% ($m \approx 0.01$) would translate in a $\sim 30\%$ degradation in the statistical error of the equation-of-state parameter w_0 . The understanding, modeling and reduction of systematic errors is an active area of research in weak lensing, and the scientific reach of cosmological surveys such as the Dark Energy Survey (DES) relies on advances in this direction. In fact, one of the science objectives of DES (Annis et al., 2010) is to understand and improve the control of systematic errors (not only associated to weak lensing but to other techniques in general) in preparation for future surveys (or Stage IV surveys, in the language of the DETF; DES is termed a Stage III survey (Albrecht et al., 2006)). The work performed in this thesis is part of this effort to advance this understanding.

1.6 The Dark Energy Survey

The Dark Energy Survey is a wide-area, multi-band (*grizY*) imaging survey that will cover 5000 deg^2 of the sky in the Southern Galactic Cap. DES plans to measure the dark energy equation of state parameter, $w(z)$ (Section 1.4) with a 5% statistical uncertainty. Its wide area and depth ($\sim 24th$ magnitude) will allow for the detection of about 100,000 galaxy clusters, and the measurement of shapes, positions and accurate photo- z 's of about 300 million galaxies up to a redshift of ~ 1.3 (when the Universe was about 1/3 of its current age). DES will also perform a SNe survey that will consist of *griz* imaging of 8 deep and 2 shallow fields of 3 deg^2 each, enabling the collection of about 4000 light curves for Type Ia SNe to $z \sim 1$. DES will also benefit from the data taken by other surveys. For instance, it will overlap with the South Pole Telescope¹³, and it will collaborate with the ESO Vista Hemisphere Survey¹⁴, which will provide deep *JHK* filters imaging over the same wide sky area, improving photo- z precision at redshifts $z = 1 - 2$, and with the ESO VIDEO Survey, which is expected to provide coincident NIR measurements for a subsample of DES

¹³<http://pole.uchicago.edu/>

¹⁴<http://www.ast.cam.ac.uk/~rgm/vhs/>

supernovae.

(a) Small Magellanic Cloud.

(b) Barred spiral galaxy NGC 1365 (Fornax galaxy cluster)

Figure 1.6: First images taken with the DES imager, DECam, during its commissioning period (September 2012). Credit: DES collaboration. Image taken from http://fnal.gov/pub/presspass/press_releases/2012/DES-DECam-201209-images.html

As part of the DES project, a 500 megapixel camera was constructed (called the Dark Energy Camera, DECam), using 62 fully-depleted, 250 μm thick, back-illuminated CCDs with a high quantum efficiency on red wavelengths (Honscheid et al. , 2008). DECam is currently (October 2012) undergoing its commissioning period (Figure 1.6), and the survey is planned to start in December 2012.

DES will measure dark energy and dark matter through the four complementary techniques mentioned in Section 1.4. This will enable important improvements in the statistical precision of cosmological parameters, as well as large systematic errors crosschecks.

1.6.1 Weak lensing in DES

The size of the PSF (~ 0.8 arcsec), survey area, and the magnitude depth of DES will give an effective number of galaxies usable for weak lensing, n_{eff} , of ~ 10 arcmin $^{-2}$, which means that DES will measure shapes of about 300 million galaxies

and cover the largest area ever surveyed for a cosmic shear analysis. This will bring down the statistical errors to unprecedented levels, and therefore it will be crucial to make sure that the systematic errors do not dominate the error budget.

The primary lensing statistic to obtain constraints on cosmological parameters (such as Ω_m , σ_8 , w_0 , and w_a) in DES will be the shear-shear power spectrum (Equation [1.106]), although other cross-correlation statistics (Equation [1.107]) are expected to be calculated as well. In DES, systematic errors are required to be subdominant compared to statistical uncertainties. In the case of weak lensing, this condition translates into requirements on image quality, stability, and accuracy of photometric redshifts. In particular, the multiplicative and additive errors for shear have to satisfy $m < 4 \cdot 10^{-3}$ and $c < 4 \cdot 10^{-4}$ for the whole area of the survey (Annis et al., 2010). The following chapters study the impact of some of the weak lensing systematic errors on these two parameters. In the next chapter, we assess the performance of the main DES pipeline by directly measuring the parameters m and c through simulations. This pipeline is an implementation of the Elliptical Gauss-Laguerre formalism detailed in Bernstein and Jarvis (2002) (see Section 2.1.1 below). Other implementations of this method have demonstrated an accuracy of $\sim 1\%$ and $\sim 0.1\%$ in the m and c parameters (Nakajima and Bernstein (2007), Heymans et al. (2006), Massey et al. (2007), Bridle et al. (2009)). In Chapters 2 and 3 we study how inaccurate knowledge of an astrometric solution (the map between detector and sky coordinates) and atmospheric dispersion can affect shear measurements, keeping as reference the requirements on m and c . Failure to meet the requirements on m and c would affect the successful achievement of DES science objectives.

Chapter 2

Testing the DES weak lensing measurement pipeline

2.1 Introduction

Weak gravitational lensing is one of the most powerful and promising techniques to measure cosmological parameters and characterize dark energy, provided that its numerous systematic errors can be appropriately modeled and kept under control. The list of systematic errors is long (Section 1.5.5), and considerable effort has been made in recent years to try to characterize them in preparation for the oncoming weak lensing surveys. In this Chapter, we describe the set of tests we developed to evaluate the performance of the PSF and gravitational shear (γ) measurement modules of the DES weak lensing measurement pipeline. To test the former, we create images of PSFs constructed from Gauss-Laguerre (see Section 2.1.1) models, then compare the results of pipeline measurements of these PSF images to the true input. The accuracy of the recovered values is compared with the DES requirements. In the case of the shear measurement module, we generate images containing galaxies and stars with known characteristics, and we explore the performance of the module in different areas of parameter space. The systematic errors in shear recovery accuracy are usually

parameterized in terms of the “multiplicative” (or calibration) and “additive” terms m and c as $\gamma_i - \gamma_i^{\text{true}} = m_i \gamma_i^{\text{true}} + c_i$ (Section 1.5.5). The multiplicative error can arise, for instance, by an inaccurate correction for the circular blurring of galaxy images due to atmospheric seeing, whereas the additive error may be due to imperfect corrections of PSF anisotropies. We are interested, in particular, in verifying that these parameters satisfy the DES specifications ($m_i < 0.004$ and $c_i < 0.0004$; requirement **R – 17** in DES Science Requirements Document V9.86, (Annis et al., 2010)). Some of the tests we perform are also part of those proposed in the DES WL Commissioning Plan document (*c.f.*, Chapter 3) on shape measurement (tests *SHA-1* and *SHA-2* (Bernstein, 2011)), and they also aim to validate the requirements on m_i and γ_i stated above.

In the next subsections (2.1.1 & 2.1.2), we give an overview of the pipeline and of the mathematical formalism of the shear measurement method (“Elliptical Gauss-Laguerre” or “Shapelets”) that the pipeline uses. We also describe, in detail, the types of simulations we create to perform our tests. Sections 2.2 and 2.3 describe these tests and the results obtained for the PSF and shear measurement modules, respectively. Finally, in Section 2.4, we discuss the implications of our tests for DES WL science.

2.1.1 The DES shear measurement pipeline and the Gauss-Laguerre expansion

The weak lensing pipeline consists of three modules¹: `findstars`, `measurepsf`, and `measureshear`. The first module, `findstars`, selects those objects from the input catalog (provided by the DES Data Management (DESDM) team) that will be used for PSF determination by using a size-magnitude diagram. The flux of the stars is expected to change, but not the size, until the detector reaches the saturation point. This implies that stars will lie on a horizontal locus in a size vs. magnitude diagram.

¹The SVN revision of the code used is 8102.

Galaxies and other celestial objects, such as cosmic rays, also become apparent in specific areas of this plane. As stars and galaxies become fainter, they start to merge in the diagram. `findstars` splits the magnitude range in different bins and creates a histogram in each bin. The stars will show up as the dominant peak, but the galaxies will be also represented by a secondary peak. By comparing their relative heights as the magnitude bin changes, `findstars` is able to identify the horizontal star locus. Recent investigation has shown that the use of the information provided by the new (v 2.14.2) `SEXTRACTOR` (Bertin and Arnouts, 1996) parameter, `spread_model`, to separate galaxies from stars, makes the algorithm more robust. This parameter has been used in other data reduction pipelines like that of the Blanco Cosmology Survey (BCS) (Desai et al., 2012).

The second module, `measurepsf`, measures a Gauss-Laguerre (see below) expansion for every star in an image and then calculates an interpolating function (2D Legendre Polynomial) for the PSF expansion at any location in the image. The third module, `measureshear`, measures the shape of each de-convolved galaxy, using the interpolated PSF function from `measurepsf`. To characterize the shapes of stars and galaxies, `measureshear` and `measurepsf` linearly decompose their two-dimensional surface brightness in the (orthonormal and complete) Gauss-Laguerre (GL) basis of the plane $\{\psi_{pq}^\sigma(r, \theta)\}$ (Bernstein and Jarvis, 2002):

$$I(r, \theta) = \sum_{p,q \geq 0} b_{pq} \psi_{pq}^\sigma(r, \theta) \quad (2.1)$$

These functions are equivalent to the “Polar Shapelets” defined by Massey and Refregier (2005). As the name suggests, Gauss-Laguerre functions are basically a product of Gaussian functions and Laguerre polynomials $L_q^{(m)}$ in polar coordinates (or a

product of Gaussians and Hermite polynomials in Cartesian coordinates):

$$\psi_{pq}^\sigma(r, \theta) = \frac{(-1)^q}{\sqrt{\pi}\sigma^2} \sqrt{\frac{q!}{p!}} \left(\frac{r}{\sigma}\right)^m e^{im\theta} e^{-r^2/2\sigma^2} L_q^{(m)}\left(\frac{r^2}{\sigma^2}\right) \quad (2.2)$$

$$(p \geq q)$$

$$m \equiv p - q$$

The GL basis functions are also eigenfunctions of the 2D Quantum Harmonic Oscillator (QHO). The excitation energy of a quantum state specified by a wave function ψ_{pq}^σ is given by $N \equiv p + q$, and its angular momentum by m . The expansion in Equation (2.1) is exact or complete if the sum goes to infinity, but in practice one must work with a finite basis. One way of doing this is to truncate the basis to a subset with $p + q \leq N$. For a fixed σ (or in general, for a given Gauss-Laguerre basis), the surface brightness profile is completely determined by its coefficient vector $\mathbf{b} = \{b_{pq}\}$ of size $(N + 1) \cdot (N + 2)/2$. Since $I(r, \theta)$ is real, these complex coefficients must be Hermitian ($b_{pq} = \bar{b}_{qp}$). It is useful to list the real degrees of freedom (d.o.f.) of these coefficients with increasing order in $N = p + q$ and decreasing order in $m = p - q$ within a given N (see Table 1). We will refer to this mapping when presenting our results of PSF measurements in the next section.

In the ‘‘Elliptical Gauss-Laguerre’’ method, the basis functions are chosen with respect to a sheared coordinate system such that a unit circle is mapped onto a stretched ellipse with a particular shape, size and orientation. By doing this, the lowest-order GL function is a 2D elliptical Gaussian. As mentioned above, the GL functions are also the eigenfunctions of the 2D QHO, and as such they have useful mathematical properties (through the second quantization formalism) that allow us to calculate the deconvolution of the PSF with the galaxy as a simple matrix inversion. In practice, however, it is more stable to express both the galaxy and the PSF in terms of GL decompositions (which, as noted above, are completely determined by their coefficient vectors, \mathbf{b}_\star and \mathbf{b}_g), convolve these two models together, and then perform a maximum-likelihood optimization to obtain the GL coefficients of the convolved

Index	Real d.o.f
0	b_{00}
1	$\Re(b_{10})$
2	$\Im(b_{10})$
3	$\Re(b_{20})$
4	$\Im(b_{20})$
5	b_{11}
6	$\Re(b_{30})$
7	$\Im(b_{30})$
9	$\Re(b_{21})$
10	$\Im(b_{21})$
\vdots	\vdots

Table 2.1: Bijective mapping between the set of natural numbers and the real d.o.f. of Gauss-Laguerre coefficients

model (whose surface brightness at pixel i we denote as I_i^m)²:

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{i \in \text{Pixels}} \frac{(I_i^o - I_i^m)^2}{\sigma_i^2} \quad (2.3)$$

In Equation (2.3), I_i^o is the surface brightness of the observed object at pixel i , measured with uncertainty σ_i . `measureshear` assigns a shape to an object in

²To be more precise, let $\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{b}_*)$ be the convolution matrix constructed from the interpolated GL star vector \mathbf{b}_* at the galaxy location (x, y) . This convolution matrix acts on the pre-seeing galaxy vector \mathbf{b}_g (which is the one we are interested in recovering) to form the observed GL vector, $\mathbf{b}_o = \mathbf{C}(\mathbf{b}_*)\mathbf{b}_g$. Thus, the observed surface brightness can be expressed as $I^o = \Psi\mathbf{C}\mathbf{b}_g = \Psi\mathbf{b}_o = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{b}_g$ (matrix form of Equation [2.1]), where $\mathbf{A} \equiv \Psi\mathbf{C}$. To invert (or rather, “pseudoinvert”, since, in general, \mathbf{A} is not square) this matrix equation and solve for the vector \mathbf{b}_g , `measureshear` writes \mathbf{A} as $\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{Q}\mathbf{R}$, where \mathbf{Q} is column-orthogonal and \mathbf{R} is upper triangular (this is known as the QR decomposition of a matrix (Golub and Van Loan, 1996)). The sought-after solution is then $\mathbf{b}_g = \mathbf{R}^{-1}\mathbf{Q}^T I^o$. It can be shown that this solution has a \mathbf{b}_g that minimizes $\|\mathbf{A}\mathbf{b}_g - I^o\|_2$, which is equivalent to Equation (2.3).

a geometric way, in the sense that it iteratively translates/shears the object until it satisfies a particular definition of roundness, and then declares the shape to be the negative of the total shear that was required to make the object look “round”. An object with a particular GL decomposition \mathbf{b} is defined to be round when the coefficients $b_{10} \in \mathbb{C}$ and $b_{20} \in \mathbb{C}$ (each one associated with the centroid and shape of the object, respectively) are equal to zero. Once a vector of GL coefficients that minimizes Equation (2.3) is found, `measureshear` uses the corresponding coefficients to check for these roundness conditions. If these are not satisfied yet, the basis ellipse is changed and the \mathbf{b} vector remeasured, until the object is round.

2.1.2 Customized tests of the DES shear measurement pipeline

In broad terms, the simulation code we wrote (called `simages`) generates a certain number of FITS³ files that contain an array of fixed number of galaxies and stars, each one with a certain surface brightness profile⁴. Their properties are specified in a parameter file. In this way we can vary one parameter at a time and study in better detail the performance of the pipeline. These kind of tests are known as “dissection tests”, as opposed to “end-to-end tests” (*e.g.*, DESDM Data Challenges⁵, GREAT Challenges (Bridle et al., 2009), (Kitchin et al., 2010)), where the simulations try to be as close as possible to the real sky.

Some of the parameters we are able to control in `simages` are:

- Surface brightness profile of stars (PSF) and galaxies (*e.g.* Sérsic [see below] with a given index n , [$n \in [1, 4]$ in our simulations], single Gauss-Laguerre components, etc.)
- Galaxy and PSF intrinsic ellipticities (e_g and $e_{1\star}$, $e_{2\star}$) (Section 1.5.3).

³Flexible Image Transport System. It is the standard for data transport in astronomy. See <http://fits.gsfc.nasa.gov/>.

⁴The `SBProfile` class written in C++ by Gary Bernstein, is used for these purposes.

⁵<https://desweb.cosmology.illinois.edu:8443/confluence/display/PUB/The+Dark+Energy+Survey+Data+Management+Project>.

- Input distortion δ (or shear γ) of galaxies (Section 1.5.3).
- Signal-to-Noise (S/N) ratio (see below for a definition) of galaxy and PSF.
- Relative size of the galaxy with respect to the PSF (or *resolution* $r \equiv r_h^g/r_h^*$ where r_h is the radius that encloses half of the total light of the model. This is also denoted by *EE50*).
- Image pixel size, dx , of the surface brightness profiles of the objects.

The Sérsic (Sérsic (1963), Sérsic (1968), Graham and Driver (2005)) surface brightness profile is defined as

$$I(r) = I_h \exp \left\{ -b_n \left[\left(\frac{r}{r_h} \right)^{1/n} - 1 \right] \right\} \quad (2.4)$$

where I_h is the intensity at the half-light radius r_h . The index n determines the shape of the profile. For the particular cases of $n = 1$ and $n = 4$ we obtain the *exponential* and *de Vaucouleurs* profiles, which have been found empirically to be an approximate fit for the light profiles of disk and elliptical galaxies, respectively. The coefficient b_n depends on the index n , and can be approximated as $b_n \approx 1.9992n - 0.3271$ for $0.5 < n < 10$ (Capaccioli, 1989). The signal-to-noise ratio (S/N , also known as “significance”, ν), used in `simages` and quoted throughout this thesis, is defined with respect to a circular object (galaxy or star) as $\hat{f}/\sigma_{\hat{f}}$, where

$$\hat{f} = \sum_{i \in \text{Pixel}} w_i I_i dx^2 = \sum_{i \in \text{Pixel}} w_i f_i, \quad (2.5)$$

$$f_i \equiv I_i dx^2$$

and

$$\sigma_{\hat{f}}^2 \equiv \text{Var}(\hat{f}) = \sum_{i \in \text{Pixel}} w_i^2 \text{Var}(f_i) \quad (2.6)$$

are estimates of the flux of the image and the variance of the estimator of the flux, respectively. In these equations, the sum is over the full list of pixels of the image. Each pixel is labeled by an integer index i , and has size, weight and surface brightness

values equal to dx , w_i and I_i . Using this definition, we would like to find an expression for the weight function that maximizes (optimizes) the average S/N ratio. Thus, using the fact that $\langle \hat{f}_i \rangle = f_i$:

$$\left. \frac{\partial \langle \nu^2 \rangle}{\partial w} \right|_{w^{\text{opt}}} = 0 \Rightarrow \left(\sum w_i^2 \text{Var}(\hat{f}_i) \right) \sum \langle \hat{f}_i \rangle - \left(\sum w_i \langle \hat{f}_i \rangle \right) \left(\sum w_i \text{Var}(\hat{f}_i) \right) = 0 \quad (2.7)$$

The last equation is satisfied by the optimal weight $w_i^{\text{opt}} = f_i / \text{Var}(f_i)$. Using this weight, the expression for S/N becomes:

$$\left(\frac{S}{N} \right)^2 = \frac{(\sum f_i^2 / \text{Var}(f_i))^2}{\sum f_i^2 / \text{Var}(f_i)} = \sum_{i \in \text{Pixel}} \frac{f_i^2}{\text{Var}(f_i)} \quad (2.8)$$

We now need an expression for the variance. In general terms,

$$\text{Var}(f_i) = N_s + (N_{bg} + N_d) + R^2 \quad (2.9)$$

where N_s is the term for shot noise (Poisson), N_{bg} and N_d are the background noise and dark current terms, respectively (both Poisson in nature too), and R represents the readout noise standard deviation (Gaussian with zero mean). We will *assume* that N_{bg} from the sky dominates the variance. In this case, $\text{Var}(f_i) \approx N_{bg} = n \, dx^2$, with $n \equiv$ number of background counts per area on the sky (*e.g.*, per arcsec²). Therefore, we obtain a final expression for the S/N :

$$\left(\frac{S}{N} \right)^2 = \sum_{i \in \text{Pixel}} \frac{I_i^2(x) \, dx^4}{n \, dx^2} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i \in \text{Pixel}} I_i^2(x) \, dx^2 \quad (2.10)$$

`simages` begins by creating circular galaxies and PSFs and then transforming them to give them intrinsic ellipticities, fluxes, and characteristic sizes, according to the specifications in the input parameter file. The centroid of the galaxy (and of the star) is then randomized within an area dictated by the pixel size, and then the galaxy is rotated to a certain angle (relevant to the so-called “ring tests”, see Section 2.3), sheared and convolved with the PSF. We draw the profiles in rectangular patches of a certain size in pixels (“postage stamps”) that are arranged in a rectangular array. Finally, we add the background noise to the whole image.

The next two sections present the main tests of the pipeline that we have been performing with the help of the simulations created by `simages`. It is worth pointing out first, however, that these customized tests have already allowed us to identify problems in the code and to implement solutions for them. Some of the solved problems are:

- Centroiding mismatch: Simple tests with exponential galaxies, Gaussian PSF and low noise ($S/N = 10^5$) resulted in a bias in the second component of the measured shear (γ_2). It was discovered that a mismatch between the pixel numbering conventions (*e.g.*, the origin starting at $(0, 0)$ as opposed to $(1, 1)$) led to a slight memory of the initial guess of the centroid that persisted over iterations. The algorithm was made more robust and a new parameter introduced in the parameter file to take this into account.
- Shapelet order of the galaxy decomposition: Initially the galaxies' GL decomposition was of low order ($N = 2$), leading to biased results. Increasing the order to $N = 6$ improved the performance of the pipeline.
- Aperture size: We were using an aperture that was only 3 times the characteristic size of the galaxy. Biases of the order of 10% were being obtained due to this. Our simulations showed that increasing that factor to 4 was enough to mitigate the error.
- Spurious trigger of flags⁶: Some galaxies were being flagged incorrectly. The code was fixed to correct for this.

⁶A flag is a variable in the code that gets triggered any time anomalies in the algorithm occur; see Section 2.3.2

2.2 PSF measurements

2.2.1 Methods

One of the most critical systematic errors in galaxy shape measurement is the correct modeling of the PSF pattern in each exposure. Therefore, we wanted to verify that the PSF measurement module (`measurepsf`) of the shear measurement pipeline is able to characterize any PSF pattern with the required accuracy for DES. In order to do this, we generated several realizations of stars whose surface brightness profiles consist of a single GL vector with arbitrarily chosen amplitudes (see Equation [2.11] below). `measurepsf` then creates a model of the PSF based on these simulated stars and then outputs a catalog with the GL coefficients it measured (normalized by the first GL component b_{00} , which is associated with the flux of the stars). We then averaged the measured vectors component-wise, and subtracted the input (true) values from this mean vector to obtain a measurement error for each real degree of freedom of the shapelet expansion. To simplify our analysis, we fixed the characteristic size of the input PSF (σ_*).⁷ However, we allowed the centroid of the PSF to vary in some cases because we expect that it will be another parameter to fit when analyzing DES data. We also studied the behavior of `measurepsf` as the stars' S/N values were changed.

The particular input surface brightness profile of the simulated stars we used is of the form (66 terms, since $N_* = 10$):

$$(b_{00}, \Re(b_{40}), \Im(b_{40}), b_{22}, \Re(b_{31}), \Im(b_{31}), \Re(b_{60}), \Im(b_{60})) = (1, 0.1, 0.1, 0.167, 0.15, 0.25, 0.2, 0.2) \quad (2.11)$$

The rest of the real degrees of freedom are set to zero.

⁷In addition, in real data the size of the PSF should be pretty close to constant across the FOV of a given exposure

2.2.2 Results

Our tests show that `measurepsf` is able to recover the input amplitudes of the stars with a measurement error lower than 1%. Figure 2.1 shows the measurement error for each GL coefficient at different S/N values and under different centroid conditions (fixed or not fixed) in the input models. The real degrees of freedom on the abscissa axis are labeled according to the mapping described in Section 2.1.1 and Table 2.1. The purple and red horizontal lines represent a 1% and 0.1% measurement error accuracy, respectively, and the green vertical dotted lines mark those coefficients different from zero in the input GL vector (Equation [2.11]). `measurepsf` is able to recover the input models to a 1% accuracy even when the centroid is allowed to float (Figures 2.1a and 2.1b). However, there are still some points that are several standard deviations⁸ away from the origin (a perfect PSF recovery would have all the points lying on the origin). This bias practically goes away when the S/N of the stars is increased by a factor of 4, bringing the measurement error to a level lower than 0.1% (Figure 2.1c).

A more detailed analysis shows that this bias can be attributed to the non-linearity of the fit for the GL parameters of the star models. As noted above, `measurepsf` actually measures normalized (by the b_{00} coefficient, which represents the flux of the decomposition) Gauss-Laguerre coefficients. This means that the quantity of interest is b_{pq}/b_{00} , which is a quotient of two linear-fit parameters that will be naturally biased, as the derivation in Equation (2.12) shows. Such bias would be absent if the fit were completely linear. The first expected deviation from zero bias in the non-zero b_{pq} coefficients roughly scales as $(S/N)^{-2}$ (see Figure 2.2):

⁸The red error bars on each point show the 1σ standard deviation on the mean value of the measured GL vectors.

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{b_{pq}}{b_{00}} &= \frac{\bar{b}_{pq} + \delta b_{pq}}{\bar{b}_{00} + \delta b_{00}} \approx \frac{\bar{b}_{pq} + \delta b_{pq}}{\bar{b}_{00}} \left(1 - \frac{\delta b_{00}}{\bar{b}_{00}} + \frac{(\delta b_{00})^2}{\bar{b}_{00}^2} \right) \\
&= \frac{\bar{b}_{pq}}{\bar{b}_{00}} - \frac{\bar{b}_{pq}}{\bar{b}_{00}^2} \delta b_{00} + \frac{\bar{b}_{pq}}{\bar{b}_{00}^3} (\delta b_{00})^2 + \frac{\delta b_{pq}}{\bar{b}_{00}} - \frac{\delta b_{pq}}{\bar{b}_{00}^2} \delta b_{00} + \frac{\delta b_{pq}}{\bar{b}_{00}^3} (\delta b_{00})^2 \\
&\Rightarrow \left\langle \frac{b_{pq}}{b_{00}} \right\rangle = \frac{\bar{b}_{pq}}{\bar{b}_{00}} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\nu^2} \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{2.12}$$

In the previous derivation, b_{pq} and b_{00} represent the non-zero and first Gauss-Laguerre coefficients of the expansion of each object, respectively; and δb_{pq} and δb_{00} the error in the measurement of their average values (denoted by a bar over them). The ratio $\nu \equiv \bar{b}_{00}/\delta b_{00}$ is defined as the significance or signal-to-noise value of the decomposition (not to be confused with the surface brightness profiles' S/N defined in Equation [2.10]). In addition, we have assumed $\langle \delta b_{pq} \rangle = \langle \delta b_{00} \rangle = \langle \delta b_{pq} \delta b_{00} \rangle = 0$ (since the orthogonality of the $\{\psi_{pq}^\sigma\}$ basis vectors implies that they will be statistically independent for background-limited observations and white noise), and dropped the third order terms in the error.

A direct comparison of the DES requirements to our results is not straightforward given that the DES science requirements do not have explicit constraints on particular parameters of a shear/PSF characterization method. Generally speaking, we would like to verify that the level of accuracy in the recovery of the PSF is such that errors in PSF shape and size do not propagate into noticeable spurious symmetric and asymmetric moments of the galaxy after deconvolution. Thus, requirements on the PSF knowledge arise from the constraints on the multiplicative and additive terms in each shear component, $m_i < 4 \cdot 10^{-3}$ and $c_i < 4 \cdot 10^{-4}$, respectively. Based on this, a more detailed calculation of PSF requirements is presented in the Weak Lensing Validation Tests document by Bernstein (2011) (*c.f.*, Chapter 3). We can carry out a similar analysis by using Equation (1.101) of Section 1.5.3:

$$\hat{e}_g = e_o \frac{r_o^2}{r_o^2 - r_\star^2} - e_\star \frac{r_\star^2}{r_o^2 - r_\star^2},$$

which describes how the galaxy shape estimate depends on the size and shape of the

observed galaxy and PSF, to first order. As indicated in that section, a fractional error in the factor multiplying the first term propagates into a calibration error (m_*), whereas an error in the second term directly propagates as a spurious additive shear (c_*). The multiplicative error is related to the dilation caused by the PSF that makes galaxies look rounder, suppressing the lensing shear. Therefore, we can associate the fractional error in the size of the PSF with the b_{11} GL coefficient as:

$$\delta b_{11}/b_{00} = \delta r_*/r_* = \delta \ln r_*, \quad (2.13)$$

where δr_* is the absolute error in the determination of r_* . On the other hand, the additive term (associated with asymmetries in the PSF which could mimic a lensing signal) relates to the error in the second term of Equation (1.101), and can be associated with the b_{20} GL coefficient as:

$$2\sqrt{2} \delta b_{20}/b_{00} = \delta(e_*) \quad (2.14)$$

The extra numerical factors come from the exact definitions of the shape, centroid and size terms as a function of GL coefficients given in Section 6.3 of Bernstein and Jarvis (2002). Taking these considerations into account, we have the following expression for the multiplicative error:

$$m_* = \frac{\partial \ln \left(1 - \frac{r_*^2}{r_o^2}\right)^{-1}}{\partial \ln r_*} \delta \ln r_* = \frac{2r_*^2}{r_o^2 - r_*^2} \delta \ln r_* = \frac{2r_*^2}{\hat{r}_g^2} \delta \ln r_* \quad (2.15)$$

If we use the DES requirements as a maximum value for m_* , and we assume that the smallest galaxy we are going to use for shape measurements is about the same size as the PSF size (*i.e.*, $r_g/r_* \approx 1$), then the error in the normalized GL b_{11} term should satisfy:

$$\delta \ln r_* = \frac{\delta b_{11}}{b_{00}} \approx \lesssim 0.002 \quad (2.16)$$

For the additive term, assuming again that the c_* will be under the value specified by the DES requirements, and that $r_g \approx r_*$, we have:

$$\frac{\delta b_{20}}{b_{00}} \lesssim \frac{\delta e_*}{2\sqrt{2}} \approx \frac{4 \cdot 10^{-4}}{2\sqrt{2}} \approx 0.0002 \quad (2.17)$$

The previous analysis implies that, in order to perform a successful PSF deconvolution to recover the shear, we need to have a complete knowledge and understanding of our PSF models to at least $O(10^{-3})$. In other words, according to our rough estimations, we should be able to recover the parameters of our PSF models (the \mathbf{b}^* coefficients, in particular those that contribute the most to the size and shape of the PSF, such as b_{11} and b_{20}) to an accuracy of about 2 parts in 1000 and 10000, in the cases of calibration and additive terms, respectively. Henrikson et al. (2008) also estimate that the relative error in the size of the PSF and the error in the PSF ellipticity should be less than about 10^{-3} in order to satisfy the constraint $\sigma_{sys}^2 < 10^{-7}$, where σ_{sys}^2 (defined in Amara and Réfrégier (2008)) quantifies the amplitude of systematic errors in lensing surveys. Our tests show that we can reach an $O(10^{-3})$ level of accuracy (< 2 parts in 1000) if we perform PSF measurements at a $S/N \gtrsim 25$ (see Figure 2.2). Yet, a larger PSF signal-to-noise ($S/N \approx 70$) would be needed to attain an accuracy of 2 parts in 10000. We should keep in mind, however, that the requirements on m_i and c_i apply to the full data set of the survey; the first year data should be subject to looser constraints. In addition, measurements from one of the internal DES Data Challenges (DC6B⁹) indicate that the number density of stars with $S/N > 70$ will be about 1.5 per arcmin², or 250 per CCD; and, if we find that the PSF model does not vary considerably along a given patch of the detector, the stars in that area can be averaged to effectively increase the detection S/N of the PSF.

⁹<https://desdb.cosmology.illinois.edu/confluence/display/TnV/DC6B>

(a) $(S/N)_\star = 25$, centroid fixed.

(b) $(S/N)_\star = 25$, centroid not fixed.

(c) $(S/N)_\star = 100$, centroid not fixed.

Figure 2.1: Measurement error (normalized by the measured b_{00} value) for each PSF GL coefficient. In the two upper panels the stars have a $(S/N)_\star = 25$, whereas in the lower one, $(S/N)_\star = 100$. The GL real degrees of freedom are labeled according to Table 2.1 (Section 2.1.1). The purple and red horizontal lines represent a 1% and 0.1% measurement error accuracy, respectively. The green vertical dotted lines mark those coefficients different from zero in the input GL vector (Equation [2.11]). The red vertical error bars represent the 1σ standard deviation on the mean of the measured GL coefficients.

Figure 2.2: Measurement error of non-zero PSF coefficients (Equation [2.11]) as a function of S/N . The bias roughly scales as $(S/N)^{-2}$ (black, solid line), see Equation (2.12).

2.3 Shear recovery: tests of the pipeline module `measureshear`

2.3.1 The Ring Test

As with `measurepsf`, the `simages` program was also used to create customized images to test the shear measurement module, `measureshear`. In most of the sim-

ulations, a random orientation was chosen for each galaxy with a given intrinsic ellipticity, and then another galaxy with the same ellipticity but rotated 90° from the first one was created. This is referred as the *ring test* (Nakajima and Bernstein, 2007), because in ellipticity space (a Cartesian plane where the axes are the two ellipticity components of the galaxies) this ensemble of galaxies forms a ring of radius e_g , the unsheared intrinsic ellipticity of the galaxies. A small (in the weak lensing sense), uniform distortion can then be applied, and the mean ellipticity over the ring gives an estimate of the shear. The ring test eliminates the variance in the mean shear that would arise from randomized intrinsic shapes, or “shape noise” (Section 1.5.3). By removing this shape noise term in the error, we do not need to average over as many galaxies as would be necessary with a random distribution of galaxies. The ring test is a useful tool that has been employed in several other simulations by the weak lensing community (*e.g.*, Massey et al. (2007), Bridle et al. (2009), Voigt and Bridle (2010)).

2.3.2 Convergence rate of the pipeline

Before investigating the accuracy of the code to recover gravitational shear, we study the conditions under which it successfully returns a shape measurement. We quantify this by calculating the fraction of objects that trigger flags in the algorithm, or *convergence rate*. So far there are 30 flags defined, and they can arise for many different reasons. Most of their names are self-explanatory:

- | | | |
|------------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|
| 1. INPUT_FLAG | 6. UNKNOWN_EXCEPTION | 11. TOO_SMALL |
| 2. TRANSFORM_EXCEPTION | 7. EDGE | 12. DECONV_FAILED |
| 3. FITTEDPSF_EXCEPTION | 8. LT10PIX | 13. SHEAR_FAILED |
| 4. TMV_EXCEPTION | 9. MEASURE_PSF_FAILED | 14. SHAPELET_FAILED |
| 5. STD_EXCEPTION | 10. NATIVE_FAILED | 15. SHEAR_REDUCED_ORD |

16. SHAPE_REDUCED_ORDER	21. SHEAR_BAD_COVAR	26. PSF_BAD_FLUX
17. SHEAR_LOCAL_MIN	22. NO_SINGLE_EP_IMAGES	27. SHAPE_BAD_FLUX
18. SHEAR_POOR_FIT	23. BKG_NOPIX	28. CENTROID_FAILED
19. SHAPE_LOCAL_MIN	24. PSF_INTERP_OUTLIER	29. SHAPELET_NOT_DECON
20. SHAPE_POOR_FIT	25. SHEAR_BAD_FLUX	30. SHEAR_DIDNT_CONVER

A completely conservative analysis would require that no flag be triggered during the run of the code in order to have confidence that the measured shape value is not biased by any of the conditions represented in the flags. However, in our simulations we have decided to tolerate some flags related to the first measurement of galaxy shapes (flags starting with the `SHAPE_` prefix), or *native fits* (before the PSF deconvolution, (Nakajima and Bernstein, 2007)), given that subsequent iterations to deconvolve the PSF from the galaxy are expected to correct for any initial mismatch. Some of these flags are not expected to be triggered at all due to the nature of our simulations. For instance, we create postage stamps that are several pixels away from each other, ensuring that each one is effectively isolated from the others. Therefore, no instances of the `EDGE` flag should be present, as they would in real-life cases where the galaxies/stars are often close to each other (“crowding”) or near the edges of the detector. Also, we do not test for the impact of an imperfect knowledge of the PSF, or for irregularities in the CCDs (non-linearities, bad columns, Charge Transfer Inefficiency (CTI), etc.), so flags associated with these issues are not expected to be triggered either.

We would like to know what level of incompleteness (convergence rate < 1) would induce values of m_i and/or c_i that are intolerable. We generate galaxies whose ellipticities follow a distribution of the form $P(e_g) \propto (1 - e_g^2)$, arrange them in perpendicular pairs to eliminate the shape noise, and then shear them according to Equation (1.91).

Figure 2.3: Multiplicative (m) error parameters for each shear component as a function of completeness of the galaxy ellipticity distribution $P(e_g) \propto (1 - e_g^2)$, with a circular and Gaussian PSF. Galaxies’ orientations are drawn from a random distribution. For each simulated galaxy another one is created with the same ellipticity but separated by 90° to reduce the shape noise, and then the whole ensemble is sheared. The most elliptical galaxies are clipped at each iteration to create an incomplete sample. The magenta, dashed lines bound a region with $|m_i| \leq 0.004$ (DES requirements). The additive term c_i was found to be consistent with zero in each case. The multiplicative error depends linearly (red line) on the incompleteness of the sample. In order to satisfy the DES requirements on m , the completeness of the sample has to be better than 99.9% (or, equivalently, the incompleteness less than 0.1%).

Figure 2.4: Convergence contours as a function of resolution and S/N (referred to as significance in this plot). The galaxies used in the top two panels have fixed intrinsic ellipticity, whereas the ellipticity of those used in the lower panel follow a distribution of the form $P(e_g) \propto (1 - e_g^2)$. 99.8% and 99.9% (*c.f.*, Figure 2.3) contours of successful convergence are demarcated by the black, dashed lines.

We then consider a form of incompleteness that would most severely bias shear: as a worst-case scenario, we gradually clip the most elliptical galaxies (creating incomplete samples) to see how the mean measured shear is affected by incompleteness. Figure 2.3 shows that a completeness of about 99.9% is necessary to have multiplicative error less than 4 parts in 1000 (the additive error was measured to be consistent with zero, as expected from the azimuthal symmetry of the input PSF, and therefore is not shown in Figure 2.3). Hence, we would like to limit subsequent tests and the real data analysis to subregions in parameter space that satisfy this convergence

condition.

The importance of improving the convergence lies in the expectation that most of the DES galaxies will be faint and small, and a minimum galaxy density of $n_{\text{eff}} = 8 \text{ arcmin}^{-2}$ (useful for lensing) must be attained in order to comply with the WL science objectives (Annis et al., 2010). To study the convergence rate of the code we varied three critical parameters: galaxy S/N , resolution, and intrinsic galaxy ellipticity e_g . We examined the convergence rate as a function of resolution and S/N for different galaxy ellipticity distributions (Figure 2.4). We performed null ring tests (zero input distortion or shear) and used an exponential profile galaxy and Gaussian circular PSF. We found that the code’s convergence rates are lower ($\lesssim 99.9\%$) as resolution and signal-to-noise ratio decrease.

It can also be observed that the zone of $\gtrsim 99.9\%$ convergence increases as the intrinsic ellipticity of the galaxy diminishes. In the case where the galaxies’ ellipticities are drawn from a distribution of the form $P(e_g) \propto (1 - e_g^2)$, the convergence pattern is very similar to that where e_g is fixed to 0.5. The results indicate that faint galaxies ($S/N \sim 15$) can be reliably used by our shape measurement code if they are marginally resolved, *i.e.*, $r > 1.2$ (in the case of $e_g = 0.2$).¹⁰ Also, in order to be able to use marginally resolved galaxies without regard to their ellipticity, a minimum cut of $S/N \gtrsim 27$ should be imposed on the detections. Since we will most likely be using galaxies with S/N as low as 15 to attain the desired number density of galaxies required for weak lensing calculations, our results indicate that improvements in the shear algorithm or calibration methods must be developed in the future.

¹⁰Galaxies useful for WL in DES will have a characteristic size no smaller than the median PSF FWHM over the whole survey, which is equal to 0."9

2.3.3 Shear recovery accuracy

Dependence on galaxy intrinsic ellipticity and resolution

The contour plots in Figure 2.4 demonstrate how the pipeline behaves as the ratio of the characteristic size of the galaxy with respect to the PSF changes. However, to study the behavior of the code under this parameter in more detail, we performed ring tests with non-zero input shear (Figure 2.5a). We used very low-noise images (as with the PSF measurements of the previous section), and we fixed the intrinsic galaxy ellipticity to the nominal value 0.2. Six different input shears, and a circular, Gaussian PSF were used in this test. For galaxies with $r \gtrsim 1$ and $\gamma^{\text{true}} \lesssim 0.075$, the multiplicative error is < 0.004 (except for γ_1 , in the cases when $r = 1.7$ and $r = 1.9$, where it goes slightly above this threshold up to 0.006). Relaxing the full-area DES requirements and allowing a calibration error of 1%, we find that all values with $r \gtrsim 0.8$ satisfy this threshold regardless of the input shear.

Figure 2.5b displays analogous plots to those shown Figure 2.5a. This time, the intrinsic ellipticity of the galaxies is changed and the galaxies are well resolved ($r = 2$). Once again the S/N ratio was fixed to a high value, and a Gaussian circular PSF model was utilized. The pipeline performs quite well ($\Delta\gamma/\gamma < 0.004$) for the range of low intrinsic e_g values ($e_g \lesssim 0.5$), although at higher ellipticities we still observe a multiplicative bias factor of about 1%.

Figure 2.5: Magnitude of the shear multiplicative error ($\Delta\gamma/\gamma = m$) as a function of resolution (top) and intrinsic ellipticity (bottom). When the resolution is varied, e_g is fixed to 0.2, whereas when e_g changes, r is set to 2. Low noise ($S/N = 10^5$) galaxies with exponential profiles (Sérsic with $n = 1$) convolved with a circular, Gaussian PSF were used. Each colored symbol represents a different input shear in a ring test. The red, solid lines represent the five-year DES requirements on m , while the magenta lines represent a 1%(0.01) bias in m .

Dependence on signal-to-noise ratio.

DES will be detecting many faint galaxies and it will be important for weak lensing to provide a highly accurate shape measurement of most of these objects in order to achieve a galaxy density of $n_{\text{eff}} = 8 \text{ arcmin}^{-2}$, as mentioned above. Therefore, we are interested in characterizing the performance of the DES shear measurement pipeline as a function of S/N , as we did in Section 2.2.2 with the PSF models. We would like to determine the S/N value needed to satisfy the constraints on m and c for each shear component. For these tests, we chose well resolved galaxies ($r = 2$) with relatively low intrinsic ellipticity ($e_g = 0.2$), but we changed the surface brightness model of the galaxies used (Sérsic with $n \in \{1, 2.5, 4\}$). For the case of Sérsic with $n = 1$ (Exponential) and Sérsic with $n = 2.5$ profiles, the top two panels in Figure 2.6 show how the shear recovery accuracy improves as S/N increases, as expected (the errors being larger in the case of the latter, though). However, a closer analysis reveals that the full-survey requirements on multiplicative shear errors are not satisfied for any value of the S/N range used (Figure 2.7). A lower S/N would suffice if we are willing to tolerate a looser constraint on m ($< 1\%$), though. In the case of galaxies that follow a Sérsic with $n = 4$ profile, an even larger bias is found (lower panel, Figure 2.6). This is evident in Figure 2.7, where the values for the m and c terms in each component exceed those obtained for the case of Sérsic with $n \in \{1, 2.5\}$ galaxies by almost one order of magnitude. Sérsic with $n = 4$ profiles are relatively steep at the center and extended at the outskirts compared to other profiles, and therefore the current order and/or compactness of the shapelet expansion might be contributing a model bias in addition to the bias due solely to noise.

(a) Sérsic $n=1$

(b) Sérsic $n=2.5$

(c) Sérsic $n=4$

Figure 2.6: Shear measurement calibration error ($\Delta\gamma_i/\gamma_i = m$) as a function of S/N for well-resolved ($r = 2$) Sérsic galaxies ($e_g = 2$) with different profile index: $n = 1$ (a), $n = 2.5$ (b), and $n = 4$ (c), convolved with a circular Gaussian PSF. Different input shear values (represented by the different colored symbols) were used in a ring test. The red, solid horizontal lines denote the DES requirement on m , while the magenta lines represent a 1% (0.01) bias in m .

Figure 2.7: Multiplicative factor and additive terms as a function of S/N derived from ring tests for Sérsic galaxies with different index $n \in \{1, 2.5, 4\}$ (all with $e_g = 0.2$) and convolved with a circular Gaussian PSF (data from Figure 2.6). The resolution is set to 2. The left column shows the results for γ_1 , and the second, for γ_2 . The red, solid horizontal lines represent the whole-survey requirements on m (<0.004) and c (<0.0004). The magenta lines represent a 1% (0.01) bias in m .

PSF anisotropy

So far, we have made use of circular PSF models, but a fundamental task of the shear measurement pipeline as a whole is to adequately correct for anisotropies in the PSF that break the assumed symmetry in the orientations of the galaxies and propagate directly into the shear power spectrum. To test for the anisotropy rejection ability of the code, we performed ring tests where the PSF was Gaussian but whose second ellipticity component departed from zero ($(e_{1\star}, e_{2\star}) = (0, 0.05)$), for a particular input shear value ($\gamma = (0.03, -0.03)$).

We calculated the measurement error in this case, and subtracted it from the measurement error that resulted in the case of a circular PSF (Figure 2.6) to obtain an estimate of the anisotropy parameter c . In both cases, an exponential ($e_g = 0.2$) galaxy profile was used. The results show that, for a $S/N \gtrsim 50$ the c terms of each component satisfy the full-survey requirements. For $S/N < 35$, the requirements are marginally satisfied in the case of γ_1 , but for γ_2 a deviation from the requirements at $S/N = 25$ is observed (Figure 2.8).

2.4 Summary and conclusion

In this Chapter we have described the set of tests we have developed to assess the performance of the shear measurement pipeline for the Dark Energy Survey. The control of systematic errors is crucial for the adequate use of weak lensing as a powerful means to know more about dark energy and the successful achievement of the science objectives of DES. In addition, the proper modeling and understanding of systematic errors is one of the main goals of DES, in preparation for upcoming galaxy surveys (Stage IV¹¹).

¹¹Using the language of the DETF

Figure 2.8: PSF anisotropy rejection. Difference of the shear measurement errors (plotted as an additive error parameter c) for an exponential galaxy ($e_g = 0.2$, $r = 2$) convolved with a Gaussian PSF with $(e_{1*}, e_{2*} = (0, 0))$, and an exponential galaxy convolved with a Gaussian PSF with $(e_{1*}, e_{2*} = (0, 0.05))$. The input shear was set to $\gamma = (0.03, -0.03)$. The red, solid horizontal lines shows a region where $|c_i| < 0.0004$ (DES full-area requirement).

We have developed software (the “`simages`” program) to create customized images that allow us to vary individual parameters of the galaxies and stars such as S/N , intrinsic ellipticity, surface brightness profile and relative sizes of the galaxies with respect to the PSF. These tests are meant to complement other types of simulations that aim to reproduce the conditions of the sky to high precision (*e.g.*, the Data Challenges of DES); they permit a more detailed and careful exploration of the optimal regions of parameter space and pinpoint parts in the algorithms that need improvements. Other shear measurement pipelines (*e.g.*, DEIMOS (Melchior et al.,

2011), Im3shape (Zuntz et al., in preparation), etc.) that also aim to eventually make use of DES data for weak lensing analysis should be able to perform successfully under these type of customized simulations, where the input shear and many of the relevant conditions (such as PSF patterns) are known and controlled in advance.

Our tests show that the PSF measurement module of the DES pipeline, `measurepsf` can recover an input PSF profile with an accuracy better than 1% at a $S/N \geq 25$, even when the centroid of the profile is left as a free parameter to fit. We have also determined that the measurement bias scales approximately as S/N^{-2} . Knowing this functional form for the bias, we established that we will be able to achieve an accuracy on the normalized parameters of our GL models (b_{pq}/b_{00}) better than 2 parts in 1000 and 2 parts in 10000 for a star S/N of approximately 25 and 70, respectively. This satisfies the approximate requirements on the GL components that we have derived from the constraints on the m and c parameters (Equations [2.16] and [2.17]). For DES, the number density of stars with $S/N \gtrsim 75$ will be about 1.5 per arcmin².

We next examined the convergence performance of the pipeline (*i.e.*, the conditions under which it successfully returns a valid answer without triggering any internal flag) as we are interested in knowing the level of incompleteness that we would be able to tolerate in subsequent simulations (and real data analysis) without inducing a significant calibration bias. We found that, in a worst-case scenario of incompleteness, in order for the induced multiplicative bias to remain under 0.004 the completeness of the galaxy sample should be better than 99.9%. This criterion helped us to define cuts in S/N , resolution, and intrinsic galaxy ellipticity parameters. We found that a sample of faint ($S/N < 15$), not too elliptical ($e_g \lesssim 0.5$), and almost marginally resolved galaxies ($r \approx 1.2$) has the required level of completeness ($> 99.9\%$). More elliptical galaxies can be included in the sample too, as long as the size of the PSF is not too dominant ($r \gtrsim 1.6$). For DES weak lensing analysis, we will use galaxies whose characteristic sizes are at least the same as those of the stars ($r \approx 1$); in this case, a complete sample, regardless of other parameters, would be attained if the S/N of the object is at least 25. Also, galaxies with $r \gtrsim 1$ and $\gamma^{\text{true}} \lesssim 0.075$ present a

multiplicative error < 0.006 . Relaxing the full-area DES requirements and allowing a calibration error of 1% ($m < 0.01$), we find that all values with $r \gtrsim 0.8$ satisfy this threshold independent of the input shear.

In general, the shear recovery accuracy on the multiplicative parameter m was demonstrated to be better than 1% at the high S/N regime. Tests for Sérsic with $n = 1$ (Exponential) galaxies with circular Gaussian PSFs in which the resolution and the intrinsic ellipticity varied resulted in a shear multiplicative error less than 1% for a large range in those parameters (Figure 2.5). However, when the S/N was allowed to change (fixing the resolution and intrinsic ellipticity to values shown not to introduce large biases in the code, namely $r = 2$ and $e_g = 0.2$), significant biases started to arise in the high-noise regime for Sérsic galaxies with different profile index ($n \in \{1, 2.5, 4\}$). The effect is better seen in Figure 2.7, where it is shown that, for Sérsic with $n = 1$ and $n = 2$ galaxies, the DES requirement on the multiplicative factor m is not satisfied for the range of S/N values used. The de Vaucouleurs galaxies (Sérsic with $n = 4$), in turn, returned values for m roughly one order of magnitude larger than those for the other types of galaxies. The results show that work still needs to be done to improve the performance of the pipeline in the high-noise regime.¹²

¹²It should be noted, too, that biases due to non-linearities in the input shear are expected to arise when the weak-lensing assumption starts to break ($\gamma_i \approx 0.1$).

Chapter 3

Astrometry validation tests for the Dark Energy Survey

3.1 Introduction

Weak gravitational shear measurement methods rely on the accurate measurement of galaxy shapes. The error due to the intrinsic galaxy shapes, or shape noise (Section 1.5.3), decreases as the number density of galaxies gets larger; therefore a large number of galaxies is needed. This implies that most of the galaxies observed by DES will be faint, so many single-exposure observations of the same patch of the sky will need to be added together to increase the detection S/N . Usually these different exposures are mis-registered (dithered) to eliminate artifacts such as cosmic rays, bad pixels, satellite and asteroid trails, etc., and the same object needs to be identified in each of the individual exposures and matched in the coaddition process to subpixel accuracy. However, we need to coadd data from the same true (sky) position, not from the same pixel location, so a very precise map from pixel to sky coordinates, or *astrometric solution*, is needed. This mapping is also non-linear due to field distortions in the camera, which are more pronounced for wide-field imagers like DECam. When deriving an astrometric solution, two kinds of matching processes take place: a global

match that makes use of an absolute catalog such as USNO (Monet, 2003) or 2MASS (Skrutskie et al., 2006), and an internal match that identifies different detections in the observed catalog that are likely to belong to the same celestial object. Both types of match require non-trivial algorithms to determine correspondences of objects in different catalogs.

The header of each FITS image has an initial astrometric solution called the World Coordinate System (WCS, Greisen and Calabretta (2002)). In DES, this solution will be improved by the (publicly available) software **SCAMP**¹ (Bertin, 2006). These solutions must be evaluated in their precision due to the high accuracy demanded by weak lensing science. For this purpose, a set of tests have been proposed and detailed in the Weak Lensing Validation Tests (WLVT) document (Bernstein, 2011), and are meant to be performed on data taken during the Commissioning and Science Verification phases of the DECam, as well on data from the actual survey. Generally speaking, the goal of these tests is to validate the performance of the weak lensing software and the compliance of the Dark Energy Survey Data Management (DESDM) simulations to the weak lensing science objectives. We also aim to establish whether the solution provided by **SCAMP** is accurate enough for weak gravitational lensing science. Another software, named **REMATCH**², has been developed within the Weak Lensing Working Group to improve, if necessary, on the astrometric solution derived by **SCAMP**.

In this Chapter we describe how we implemented some of the tests of the accuracy of the DES astrometric solution proposed in the WLVT document. The next section describes the general structure of the initial WCS pixel-to-sky coordinates mapping of each exposure. We also briefly describe the software **SCAMP** that will be used by the DESDM team to produce a more refined astrometric solution. Section 3.2 describes in more detail the astrometry tests we implement and their direct relation to the DES Science Requirements. We will give a brief description of **REMATCH** in Section

¹v.1.7.0

²<http://www.physics.upenn.edu/~garyb/ReMatch.pdf>

3.2.2, and explain how it compares to **SCAMP**. The astrometry test of the WLVT that we have implemented is described in Section 3.3, along with the results obtained of simulated data from the Data Challenges 5 (DC5B) and 6 (DC6B) from DESDM and real data taken with the Wide Field Imager (WFI) ³ and for the Blanco Cosmology Survey (BCS) (Desai et al., 2012). Finally, we summarize and conclude in Section 3.4.

3.1.1 Astrometric Solution for DES

For DES, the transformation from pixel to celestial coordinates is stored in the header of each FITS image as the WCS and performed in four steps (Nielsen, 2011):

- Pixel coordinates (x_p, y_p) to tangent plane coordinates (x, y) :

$$\begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \text{CD1.1} & \text{CD1.2} \\ \text{CD2.1} & \text{CD2.2} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x_p - \text{CRPIX1} \\ y_p - \text{CRPIX2} \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.1)$$

- Tangent plane coordinates (x, y) to “standard coordinates” (ξ, η) :

$$\begin{aligned} \xi &= \sum_{i=0}^{N_{\text{pixels}}} \sum_{j=0}^i a_{ij} x^{i-j} y^j \\ \eta &= \sum_{i=0}^{N_{\text{pixels}}} \sum_{j=0}^i b_{ij} x^{i-j} y^j \end{aligned} \quad (3.2)$$

- Standard coordinates (ξ, η) to native spherical coordinates (ϕ, θ)

$$\begin{aligned} \phi &= \arg(-\eta, \xi) \\ \theta &= \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{180^\circ}{\pi \sqrt{\xi^2 + \eta^2}} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (3.3)$$

³<http://www.eso.org/lasilla/instruments/wfi/index.html>

- Native spherical coordinates (ϕ, θ) to celestial spherical coordinates (α, δ^4) (right ascension and declination):

$$\begin{aligned}\alpha &= \alpha_p + \arg(\sin \theta \cos \delta_p - \cos \theta \sin \delta_p \cos(\phi - \phi_p), -\cos \theta \sin(\phi - \phi_p)) \\ \delta &= \sin^{-1}(\sin \theta \sin \delta_p - \cos \theta \cos \delta_p \cos(\phi - \phi_p))\end{aligned}\tag{3.4}$$

The terms of the transformation from pixel coordinates to a plane tangent to the Celestial Sphere, CDi_j , and the reference pixels $CRPIXi$ of Equation (3.1), are stored as keywords in the header of each FITS exposure image. These terms follow the TPV WCS convention.⁵ The polynomial coefficients a_{ij} and b_{ij} of Equation (3.2) are also stored in the header as the PVi_m keywords. The transformation from standard coordinates (ξ, η) to native spherical coordinates (ϕ, θ) is also known as the *gnomonic* projection of the sphere on the plane. This is an inversion of the transformation equations $\xi = (180^\circ/\pi) \sin \phi \cos \theta$ and $\eta = (180^\circ/\pi) \cos \phi \cot \theta$, and it is known as the TAN projection in the FITS (pseudo) standard. Finally, the transformation shown in Equation (3.4) is just a rotation of spherical coordinates specified by its three Eulerian angles. If three consecutive rotations about the Z-, X-, and Z-axis are considered, these angles are simply given by $(\alpha_p + 90^\circ, 90^\circ - \delta_p, \phi_p - 90^\circ)$, where (α_p, δ_p) and ϕ_p are the celestial coordinates and longitude of the native pole, respectively. In zenithal projections⁶ such as the gnomonic projection, the pole of the native system (α_p, δ_p) and the reference point of the celestial coordinates, (α_0, δ_0) , coincide. These coordinates are specified by the $CRVALj$ keywords in the FITS header. In turn, the native longitude of the celestial pole is specified by the keyword `LONPOL`.

In the case of the Dark Energy Survey, the astrometric solution will be derived using the program `SCAMP`. As input, `SCAMP` takes a catalog with the weighted Gaus-

⁴Not to be confused with the parameterization of shear in terms of distortion that uses the same greek letter, introduced in Chapter 1 and used in Chapter 2

⁵<http://fits.gsfc.nasa.gov/registry/tpvwcs.html>

⁶A zenithal projection is one that preserves directions and angular relationships. It is also known as azimuthal projection.

sian centroids of the objects in all exposures. This catalog is usually obtained by running the `SEXTRACTOR` detection software (Bertin and Arnouts, 1996). `SCAMP` then matches the exposures with an absolute astrometric reference catalog and derives an astrometric solution by performing a χ^2 minimization of the quadratic sum of differences in positions between detections that are likely to represent the same object in different fields. In the process, `SCAMP` produces a model by compounding two types of functions: a map from the detector pixels to a plane tangent to the optical axis of the telescope (a cubic polynomial per CCD and filter), and a map from tangent plane to sky coordinates that should handle effects such as differential refraction (*c.f.*, Chapter 3) and stellar aberration. The former is referred as the *instrument solution* and the latter as the *exposure solution*⁷.

3.2 Weak Lensing Validation Tests: astrometry

Once an astrometric solution is obtained, we need to verify that the mapping is within the desired accuracy to perform weak lensing science and that it satisfies the science requirements of the survey. In order to accomplish this, a set of validation tests have been designed within the Weak Lensing Working Group and are explained in the WLDT document. These tests are not only meant to validate the accuracy of the astrometric solutions, but also to evaluate the performance of the software that was designed to address other important sources of systematic errors in weak lensing, such as the construction of adequate PSF models, the accuracy of shape measurements (ring tests and customized tests as described in Chapter 2) and the accuracy of the photometric redshifts obtained. The tests are to be executed on the Data Challenges simulations provided by DESDM, and on real data from previous surveys (*e.g.*, the BCS), the DECam Commissioning and Science Verification periods, and from regular observations taken during the survey.

⁷In reality, `SCAMP`, like the FITS standard, composes the exposure solution first, which is the opposite of the physically proper order.

To successfully perform the tests, it is crucial to obtain images during certain specific conditions. For instance, the same field should be observed at different airmass values and filters in order to characterize the effects of differential atmospheric diffraction (*AST* – 6, Chapter 4), and the same objects should be detected at different parts of the focal plane under the same filter to sample different scales up to the size of the whole array. For each test, success criteria and remedial actions are defined.

3.2.1 Relevant requirements for astrometry

The DES science requirements relevant for astrometry described in the Science Requirements (SR) document are:

- **R – 14** The absolute sky position of bright stars in both the individual images and the coadded image should be measured to an rms of $\lesssim 100$ milliarcseconds (mas) on all scales. Absolute positions will be reported in the J2000 system.
- **R – 15** The centroid of the images of the same star in adjacent passbands of the coadd should agree to within 100 mas, over the range of airmasses allowed by the survey.
- **R – 16** The rms of the centroids of each bright star in a set of all overlapping exposures that contain it should be no larger than 15 mas. The position measured in a coadd image must be mapped to the corresponding position in the overlapping input images with an accuracy of 15 mas or better. This requirement is for each bandpass individually.

These requirements are part of the “Level 2” requirements in the SR document, and they follow from the requirements that specify the design parameters of the survey (termed “Level 1” requirements). Both types of science requirements directly flow from the Science Objectives of DES, namely to increase the DETF figure of merit⁸ by

⁸This figure of merit is proportional to the inverse of the area in the w_0 - w_a plane that encloses the 95% CL region. The parameters w_0 and w_a are defined in Section 1.4.

at least a factor of three compared to Stage II experiments (Albrecht et al., 2006) by using the four main techniques to know about dark energy that were listed in Section 1.4, and to improve the understanding and control of the systematic errors associated with those techniques.

Requirement **R – 14** has to do with the fact that the images of stars on single-epoch exposures must be aligned to better than a third of a pixel so that the PSF in the coadded image is not degraded for photometry, whereas **R – 15** ensures the control of systematic errors in aperture photometry that could potentially arise because of centroid shifting due to atmospheric dispersion (Chapter 4). For weak lensing, we are mainly interested in validating **R – 16**, and therefore the astrometry tests of the WLVT document will aim mainly to satisfy this requirement. If there is any misalignment of the centroids of several different individual exposures, a coadded galaxy may appear more elongated than its true shape. This can mimic a lensing signal and therefore a centroid error δx propagates as an additive term c (Chapter 2) in the shear estimate of the galaxy in the form $\sim (\delta x)^2/r^2$, where r is a characteristic size of the galaxy. We note that this is analogous to the effect caused by atmospheric refraction, which will be studied in more detail in Chapter 4. Therefore the square root of Equation (4.14) (for the case of DES requirements) gives us an estimate of the expected magnitude of δx , ~ 0.024 arcsec, which is roughly consistent with the actual number quoted **R – 16** (15 mas). Failure to satisfy this requirement would imply that we cannot use this centroid in the individual (single epoch) images, and thus we would have to centroid each exposure individually, effectively decreasing the number of galaxies usable for weak lensing by about half. Such a reduction in galaxy numbers would directly affect the weak lensing science, preventing the achievement of the DES Science Objectives to the required statistical and systematic precision.

As described in the WLVT document, there are several effects that can cause astrometric errors (including detector defects, CCD non-uniformities, misalignments, differential atmospheric refraction (*c.f.*, Chapter 4), stellar aberration, etc.). We will have to determine whether the SCAMP solution will suffice to satisfy **R – 16**, or if we

will need to use an improved astrometric solution (with the program `REMATCH`, see next section). In order to assess this, the astrometry tests will help us in answering relevant questions (*e.g.*, related to the stability over time, robustness and variability of the solution) to develop an astrometric model accurate enough for weak lensing.

3.2.2 Improved astrometric solution with `REMATCH`

The `REMATCH` program is similar in structure to `SCAMP`. As input, it uses a catalog of detections in different exposures, fields, filters and possibly with different instruments, to identify and match together those that are likely to belong to the same object. A reference catalog (*e.g.*, 2MASS) is used to generate an absolute match. `REMATCH` then varies the parameters of the (previously specified) functional form of the astrometric model, and, if desired, performs an optimization in the χ^2 sense (dubbed “re-fit,” since most likely it will be an improvement over an already existent astrometric solution), minimizing the dispersion of the sky coordinates of the detections within a single match. A set of statistics on the astrometric residuals and the mismatches is reported. If the re-fit is performed, a fraction of the matches is reserved to be used as a validation set after the fit is done. This is a feature that is not present in `SCAMP`. In fact, `REMATCH` also presents other important differences with `SCAMP`. While the latter can start its matching process with no *a priori* information, `REMATCH` assumes that each image has an initial WCS (Section 3.1.1) astrometric mapping that is accurate enough to place different detections of the same object from different images (and the reference catalog) close to each other.⁹ The re-fitting process is left as an option by the code in case we are interested in assessing the accuracy of the input astrometric solution. In comparison to `SCAMP`, `REMATCH` also performs a more robust outlier rejection after each iteration of the optimization fit to achieve the highest accuracy in the solutions. Additionally, in order to be able to capture all possible variations, `REMATCH` gives more flexibility in how the solution can be modeled (*e.g.*, polynomials with different

⁹In fact, a good input catalog for `REMATCH` is the output from `SCAMP`.

degrees for the instrument and exposure solutions).

3.3 Results

The list of astrometry tests (denoted by “*AST-1*”, “*AST-2*”, and so on), acceptance criteria, and remedial actions for each one can be found in Section 2 of the WLVT document. They are meant to be implemented as back-end codes to the `REMATCH` code, using the information provided by its standard output or standard error files (or both). We characterize the resulting astrometric residuals (the difference between each detection and the mean of all detections), by calculating the variation of their magnitude (rms), or by binning them into quantities of interest such as the position in the focal plane, color, airmass of the exposures, etc. In this section we present the results on *AST-4*. We also give a description of the *AST-6* test and how it should be performed, because its implementation should be slightly different from what is outlined in the current version of the WLVT document. The *AST-6* test is closely related to the effects of atmospheric dispersion on weak lensing measurements, and a more detailed study of this effect will be presented in Chapter 4.

3.3.1 *AST-4*: Pixel-based mean astrometric residual

The WLVT document describes this tests as follows:

For each region of the focal plane of some size (e.g., 20×20 pixels), average the astrometric residuals of all objects detected in this region. Plot the residuals for each CCD as a vector diagram. A special case is to bin the objects vs. distance from the CCD edge, to measure any “glowing edge” displacement that is not being captured by the instrumental model. A second special case is to bin finely by x pixel coordinate, then create a

periodogram to find periodic variations in pixel size. Likewise in y .

Acceptance criterion: all residuals should be much less than 15 mas. Any residual pattern visible indicates an inadequacy of the instrumental distortion model that should trigger an alteration to the astrometric model.

To demonstrate the performance of the software we wrote to implement this test, we have used catalogs from the DC5B and DC6B simulations, and real images taken with the Wide Field Imager¹⁰ (WFI) and with the MOSAIC camera for the Blanco Cosmology Survey. Since the refitting step is optional in **REMATCH**, we are able to compare the results before and after improving the initial astrometric solution provided by DESDM (Figure 3.1). We found that the refit by **REMATCH** was necessary to decrease the magnitude of the residuals to tolerable levels (note the difference in scales and how the global “dilation” structure visible on the pre-fit images disappears after the refit). We would also like to examine the astrometric residuals’ structure in each individual detector. In Figure 3.2 it can be observed that, in the case of the BCS data, a certain structure (peaks and troughs) still remains after the new solution has been calculated, hinting that a modification in the functional models should be performed. For the data taken with the WFI (Figure 3.3), we set an artificial requirement on the median magnitude of the residuals per CCD (15 mas). For DES, we would like to develop simple metrics like this that can act as flags indicating that we should pay attention to a certain CCD/exposure/focal plane region.

One of the main goals of the *AST* tests is to identify features or variations in the data to modify astrometric solutions accordingly in order to satisfy the DES requirements. One such feature is the so-called “glowing-edge” effect, known to be present in the DECam CCDs (Kuhlmann et al., 2011). The glowing-edge effect arises as a consequence of the distorted electric fields near the edge of the CCDs, effectively increasing the size of the pixels. This is expected to propagate into a stretching of the astrometric residuals.

¹⁰<http://www.eso.org/sci/facilities/lasilla/instruments/wfi/>. Data provided by Daniel Grün (University Observatory Munich, Scheinerstrasse 1, 81679 Munich, Germany).

Figure 3.1: Mean of the vector fields of astrometric residual for DC5B ($\approx 20 \text{ deg}^2$) and DC6B ($\approx 200 \text{ deg}^2$) data before (left column) and after (right column) refitting the DESDM astrometric solution with REMATCH. Each vector field represents an average over the total number of detectors (62 $2k$ by $4k$ science detectors in DECam), and each arrow, in turn, represents the mean astrometric residuals over rectangular regions of certain size. Note the change of scale before and after the refit. The inward pointing arrows in the borders are caused by the “glowing edges” of the CCDs.

BCS astrometric residuals per CCD (mean over all exposures)

- 0.056 pixels (15 mas)

Figure 3.2: Astrometric residuals of data from BCS along the focal plane (8 $2k$ by $4k$ CCDs). Each vector field represents an average over all exposures. The typical magnitude of the residuals is shown as the top of each CCD as the median value. The astrometric solution has been improved with REMATCH.

WFI astrometric residuals per CCD (mean over all exposures)

– 0.063 pixels (15 mas)

Figure 3.3: Astrometric residuals of data from WFI along the focal plane (8 $2k$ by $4k$ CCDs). Each vector field represents an average over all exposures. The typical magnitude of the residuals is shown as the top of each CCD as the median value. The CCDs in red have a median residual magnitude larger than a fixed threshold of 15 mas. The astrometric solution has been improved with REMATCH.

This effect was incorporated into the DC5B and DC6B simulations, and we were able to identify it with our code, as can be appreciated by the inward-pointing large arrows in each panel of Figure 3.1, and in more detail in the two panels of Figure 3.4, where we group the residuals in vertical bins.

The code to implement the *AST* – 4 test also looks for periodic variations in the residuals signals. These could arise, for instance, from the fact that the physical pixels on the CCDs are not perfect squares. Three-phase CCDs, like those used in DECam and in many other astronomical detectors, require a minimum of seven masks that have to be matched together (Janesick 2001). Each mask is optically projected on a silicon wafer, and this projection-printing process is usually stepped across the wafer when making large CCDs on large wafers. The stepping process is not perfect, and therefore the pixels that are created at the edges of the projected masks will not have exactly the same size as the rest, potentially imprinting characteristic length scales into the detectors. This effect was observed in the former WFPC2 of the HST, where approximately every 34th row was about 3% narrower than the others (Shaklan et al. (1995), Anderson and King (1999)). To perform this analysis, we calculated periodograms¹¹ with our simulated and real data, but we did not find any significant signal. However, to test that the code is able to identify underlying periodic signals in the data, we added an artificial periodic signal (sawtooth function with amplitude of 10 mas and period of 14 pixels) to the DC5B data. The periodogram successfully identified the period of this perturbation (Figure 3.5).

¹¹A periodogram is a mathematical tool similar to the Fourier transform that calculates the significance of different frequencies in time -series data, thus helping in the identification of intrinsic periodic signals.

(a) DC5B: after refit

(b) DC5B: after refit, zoom of left-hand side of (a).

Figure 3.4: DC6B astrometric residuals binned by columns. The two peaks in the top panel represent the glowing-edge effect that was also visible in the edges of the vector fields in Figure 3.1. A zoom of the left part is shown in the bottom panel, where it is seen that the glowing-edge effect can be approximated by an exponential function of the distance from the the edge of the detector.

Figure 3.5: Periodogram of DC5B signal with an added artificial sawtooth function with period in “x” of 14 pixels and an amplitude of 10 mas. This input period was successfully identified by the test.

3.3.2 AST-6: Differential refraction tests

Atmospheric refraction has the effect of shifting the images of objects by an amount $R(\lambda, z_a)$ (where z_a is the apparent zenith angle) along the zenith direction. This in turn induces a shift in the centroid, \bar{R} , that is a function of the spectrum of the object, the instrumental response function, and z_a . As a consequence, when

stacking several single-epoch exposures taken at different airmasses/filters to create a stacked image, the mean refraction on the stars and galaxies will differ by an amount $\Delta\bar{R} \propto \tan z_a$, causing a coherent spurious elongation in the galaxies (see Chapter 4). Therefore, if we have N detections of the same celestial object with coordinates (x_i, y_i) ($i \in [1, N]$), each one will suffer a shift $\Delta\bar{R}_i = \Delta\bar{R}_0 \tan(z_a)_i$ from their true positions $(\tilde{x}_i, \tilde{y}_i)$:

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{x}_i &= (x_i - \Delta\bar{R}_0 \tan(z_a)_i \sin \theta_i) \\ \tilde{y}_i &= (y_i - \Delta\bar{R}_0 \tan(z_a)_i \cos \theta_i)\end{aligned}\tag{3.5}$$

In Equation (3.5), θ represents the *parallactic angle* of the detection. This is the angle on the sky between the great circle that passes through the detection and the zenith (also known as the meridian) and the great circle that goes through the same detection and the celestial poles. Using the “four-parts formula” of spherical trigonometry (Donnay, 2007), we can express the parallactic angle as a function of the hour angle H (the angle on the sky between the meridian and the great circle that passes through the zenith of the object and the celestial poles), the declination δ of the object, and the latitude λ of the telescope¹²:

$$\tan \theta = \frac{\sin H}{\cos \delta \tan \lambda - \sin \delta \cos H}\tag{3.6}$$

For this test, we would like to fit for each $\Delta\bar{R}_0$ term through the optimization of the following function:

$$\chi^2 = \sum_i^N \frac{(\tilde{x}_i(\Delta\bar{R}_0) - \bar{x}(\Delta\bar{R}_0))^2}{(\sigma_i^x)^2} + \sum_i^N \frac{(\tilde{y}_i(\Delta\bar{R}_0) - \bar{y}(\Delta\bar{R}_0))^2}{(\sigma_i^y)^2},\tag{3.7}$$

where the errors in the positions are given by σ_i^x and σ_i^y , and the weighted means defined as:

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{x}(\Delta\bar{R}_0) &= \frac{\sum_i^N \tilde{x}_i(\Delta\bar{R}_0)/(\sigma_i^x)^2}{\sum_i^N 1/(\sigma_i^x)^2} \\ \bar{y}(\Delta\bar{R}_0) &= \frac{\sum_i^N \tilde{y}_i(\Delta\bar{R}_0)/(\sigma_i^y)^2}{\sum_i^N 1/(\sigma_i^y)^2}\end{aligned}\tag{3.8}$$

¹²These quantities should be available in the header of each exposure file.

To calculate the magnitude of this effect and implement this test, we need to find the best estimate of the parameter $\Delta\bar{R}_0$, and of its error $\sigma_{\Delta\bar{R}_0}$ (68% confidence-level interval) for each match (a set of detections that are suspected to belong to the same object). They both can be found by evaluating the derivatives of Equation (3.7) (abusing notation and denoting the best-estimate parameter as $\Delta\bar{R}_0$ too):

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial\chi^2}{\partial\Delta\bar{R}_0}\Big|_{\Delta\bar{R}_0} &= 0 \\ \left[\frac{1}{2}\frac{\partial^2\chi^2}{\partial\Delta\bar{R}_0^2}\Big|_{\Delta\bar{R}_0}\right]^{-1} &= \sigma_{\Delta\bar{R}_0}^2 \end{aligned} \quad (3.9)$$

This test has no explicit acceptance criteria, since the effect depends directly on the atmosphere. However, we would like to be able to derive models of this effect and/or devise appropriate corrections (*e.g.*, the color correction proposed in Section 4.5), if necessary.

3.4 Summary and conclusion

The use of stacked images (coadded images) is crucial to accomplish the science objectives of the Dark Energy Survey. In particular, weak lensing techniques that make use of multiple shear measurements in different exposures rely on prior object detection in these increased S/N stacked images. However, mis-registration of centroids from single exposures can propagate into a spurious shape. Failure to accurately measure the centroid on the coadd image would imply that the (lower S/N) single-epoch images would have to be used to determine the objects centroids instead, effectively decreasing the number of galaxies usable for weak lensing by about 50%. The stacking of images is performed by using sky coordinates, not pixel coordinates, and therefore it is crucial to ensure that the map between these two reference frames, or astrometric solution, is highly accurate.

In this chapter we have described the set of tests designed to validate the accuracy of the astrometric solution provided by DESDM, which relies on the use of the software

SCAMP. Another software, REMATCH, has been developed to improve on the astrometric solution, if necessary, to satisfy the requirements. These tests are proposed in the Weak Lensing Validation Tests (WLVT) document, and make up part of a larger set of tests that include systematics related to weak lensing science (shape measurements for shear determination, photometry, and PSF modeling). In particular, we have demonstrated with simulated and real data the functioning of the software we wrote to implement one of the tests (*AST-4*) which studies the structural variation of the astrometric residuals as a function of focal plane positions. We have also shown that we are able to identify unexpected features in the signal, such as the “glowing edge” effect and periodic variations in the pixel sizes.

Future directions for research include the implementation of tests related to the time stability of the astrometric solution (*AST-5*), the final implementation of the test *AST-6*, and tests related to the impact on Charge Transfer Inefficiency (Janesick, 2001) on astrometric residuals (*AST-7*).

Chapter 4

Atmospheric dispersion effects in weak lensing measurements

The work presented in this Chapter was accepted for publication in the *Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific*:

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4.1 Introduction

Weak gravitational lensing (WL) can be used for high-precision measurements of the expansion history of the Universe and the evolution of gravitational potentials within it (Mellier, 1999; Réfrégier, 2003; Hoekstra and Jain, 2008). The WL effect by large-scale structure is best detected as a coherent elongation of background galaxy images, “cosmic shear,” which induces an RMS shift in axis ratios of only $\approx 1\%$ or less for cosmologically distant source galaxies. Several ground-based surveys of $> 1000 \text{ deg}^2$ are commencing this year, including the 5000 deg^2 *Dark Energy Survey*

(DES)¹, with the goal of measuring the amplitude and redshift dependence of cosmic shear to high precision. A yet larger and deeper survey project for late in this decade, the *Large Synoptic Survey Telescope* (LSST)², is under intensive development.

Ground-based visible observations are subject to atmospheric refraction, shifting each photon toward the zenith by an angle $R(\lambda, z_a)$ that depends on wavelength and on apparent zenith angle z_a . For finite-bandwidth observations, there are two measurable consequences: first, a centroid shift

$$\bar{R} = \frac{\int d\lambda R(\lambda, z_a) F(\lambda) S(\lambda)}{\int d\lambda F(\lambda) S(\lambda)} \quad (4.1)$$

that depends on z_a , the instrumental response function $F(\lambda)$, and the source spectrum $S(\lambda)$. Additionally the dispersion stretches the image along the zenith, which can be quantified by the photon-weighted second central moment of the dispersion kernel:

$$V \equiv \frac{\int d\lambda [R(\lambda, z_a) - \bar{R}]^2 F(\lambda) S(\lambda)}{\int d\lambda F(\lambda) S(\lambda)} \quad (4.2)$$

Like any other instrumental distortion or convolution of the galaxy images, this coherent vertical elongation of the galaxy images will be mistaken for WL shear if not removed. The standard strategy in WL observing is to use stellar images to estimate the instrumental point spread function (PSF), interpolating the stars' PSFs to the location of each galaxy, and then effect some limited form of deconvolution to extract the “pre-seeing” shape of the galaxy free of instrumental effects. In its simplest form, this instrumental correction amounts to subtracting the intensity-weighted second moments of the PSF from those observed for the galaxy to estimate the pre-seeing moments. If the atmospheric dispersion of the galaxies and stars are the same, then this stellar PSF correction will automatically correct the galaxy images for the dispersion V .³ If, however, a galaxy's V differs by an amount ΔV from the mean stellar

¹<http://www.darkenergysurvey.org/>

²<http://www.lsst.org/lsst/>

³To be precise, the dispersion acts as a convolution, like the PSF, only if the galaxy's shape is constant across the band, *i.e.* the galaxy has homogeneous color. We will ignore in this work the complications of combining atmospheric dispersion with color gradients, as they produce shear errors at lower order.

V used to estimate the PSF, then the inferred galaxy shape will be incorrect and propagate to cosmic shear errors. Our goal is to calculate the size of this effect, see if it will contribute a significant error to the cosmological results of DES or LSST, and evaluate some rudimentary techniques for eliminating the problem.

Since cosmic-shear measurements are not affected by small shifts in the *positions* of galaxy images, we are less concerned with the centroid shift \bar{R} of the galaxy image than with the broadening V . Suppose, however, that we intend to combine information from exposures at multiple hour angles and/or filters, for instance by stacking the images before measuring shapes. The registration of images will normally be done by forcing overlap of stellar images. Spectral differences between the galaxy and the mean calibrating star will induce a difference $\Delta\bar{R}$ in their mean refractions which depends on filter and hour angle. The stacked image will register the stars properly but not the galaxy, broadening the stacked galaxy image and hence producing a coherent shape error which again is confused with cosmic shear. Since both DES and LSST plan to combine many exposures to produce a single galaxy shape, we estimate $\Delta\bar{R}$ and determine whether it causes cosmic-shear errors comparable to the statistical errors of these surveys. This problem can be avoided by leaving the galaxy centroid free to differ among exposures in a shape analysis—but this typically requires that the galaxy have high signal-to-noise ratio in a single exposure, which precludes use of most of the galaxies detectable with the full combined survey data.

The effect of atmospheric dispersion on weak lensing shear measurements was crudely estimated by Kaiser et al. (1995), who determined that it should be unimportant to the measurement of galaxy cluster masses. In the intervening 15 years, however, WL observers have become far more ambitious, aiming to measure the much smaller cosmic-shear signal to high precision, so it is necessary to re-evaluate these limits, especially since neither the DES nor LSST optics incorporate atmospheric dispersion correctors. Jee and Tyson (2011) investigate the impact of atmospheric dispersion on the LSST observations, but only with the criterion that the dispersion V be a small contributor to the overall size of the PSF—they did not investigate

the much stricter criterion that V be correctable to a small fraction of the expected cosmic-shear signal.

In the next section we derive requirements on $\Delta\bar{R}$ and ΔV such that they will not bias cosmic-shear measurements at the level of the statistical errors of the DES and LSST surveys. Then Section 4.3 describes our methods for estimating these quantities, and Section 4.4 gives the resultant values in the *griz* filters for a range of galaxy types and redshifts. Having demonstrated that atmospheric dispersion is indeed a significant issue in all but the z band, we ask in Section 4.5 whether simple color-based corrections to $\Delta\bar{R}$ and ΔV can recover the required accuracy. We conclude with an outlook in Section 4.6.

4.2 Tolerable levels of atmospheric dispersion

4.2.1 Effect of dispersion on measured shear

We use a simplified model of WL shear measurement to make rough estimates of the tolerable levels of $\Delta\bar{R}$ and ΔV for cosmic-shear experiments. Galaxies are assigned shapes via their intensity-weighted second central moments

$$I_{\mu\nu} \equiv \frac{1}{f} \int dx dy I(x, y) (\mu - \bar{\mu})(\nu - \bar{\nu}), \quad (4.3)$$

$$\bar{\mu} \equiv \frac{1}{f} \int dx dy I(x, y) \mu, \quad (4.4)$$

$$f \equiv \int dx dy I(x, y) \quad (4.5)$$

where $I(x, y)$ is the surface brightness distribution of the source. In practice these integrals have divergent noise so must be bounded by some window function, which complicates the measurement but has little impact on our estimates of the effect of the (small) atmospheric dispersion on the measured shapes. The ellipticities are assigned

as

$$e_1 \equiv \frac{I_{xx} - I_{yy}}{I_{xx} + I_{yy}} \quad (4.6)$$

$$e_2 \equiv \frac{2I_{xy}}{I_{xx} + I_{yy}}. \quad (4.7)$$

and we can also assign the galaxy a second-moment-based radius, usually quite similar to its half-light radius,

$$r^2 \equiv (I_{xx} + I_{yy}). \quad (4.8)$$

The two components (γ_1, γ_2) of the applied gravitational lensing shear are estimated as $2\gamma_i \approx \langle e_i \rangle$, where the average is taken over the ensemble of galaxies in a selected region of sky position and source redshift.

These formulae require access to the galaxy's intensity $I^g(x, y)$ *before* any instrumental distortions, but we only have access to the observed I^o *after* convolution with the PSF (including atmospheric dispersion components) I^* . For present purposes it is a good approximation that:

1. The second central moments of the observed image are the sum of those from the galaxy and the PSF, which means that the galaxy moments can be estimated as $I_{\mu\nu}^g = I_{\mu\nu}^o - I_{\mu\nu}^*$. This holds exactly for shape measurements with unweighted second moments, which are not practical. However the additivity of second moments under convolution also holds for Gaussian galaxies and PSFs, hence we can expect this relation to be a good approximation for shape measurements based on Gaussian-weighted moments, such as Kaiser et al. (1995).
2. The effect of atmospheric dispersion is to boost slightly the second moment of the PSF in the zenith direction (call this the x direction), $I_{xx}^* \rightarrow I_{xx}^* + V$. This relation is exact for unweighted second moments, but is also a very good approximation for Gaussian PSFs in the limit when the atmospheric dispersion is much smaller than the PSF itself—which is certainly true here. The same boost is given to I_{xx}^o , and the subtraction will cancel V in the estimate of intrinsic moments if our PSF is correctly calculated for the galaxy.

Under these conditions we see that a small error $\Delta V \ll r^2$ in the estimate of the V for a galaxy's PSF will result in an error in the zenith second moment, $I_{xx}^g \rightarrow I_{xx}^g + \Delta V$, propagating to shape errors

$$e_1 \rightarrow e_1 \left(1 - \frac{\Delta V}{r^2} \right) + \frac{\Delta V}{r^2} \quad (4.9)$$

$$e_2 \rightarrow e_2 \left(1 - \frac{\Delta V}{r^2} \right). \quad (4.10)$$

The shear estimate on a patch of sky is one-half the average galaxy ellipticity. In the shear-measurement literature it is typical to distinguish a *multiplicative* shear error m and an *additive* shear error c as $\gamma_i^{\text{est}} = (1 + m_i)\gamma_i^{\text{true}} + c_i$ (Section 1.5.5). Comparing to the above, we infer that the atmospheric dispersion errors propagate to a multiplicative shear error

$$m = \left\langle \frac{\Delta V}{r^2} \right\rangle, \quad (4.11)$$

where the average is over the galaxies in a chosen bin of sky area and source redshift. The dispersion error also produces an additive shear error in the zenith direction of very similar amplitude, $c_1 \approx m/2$.

4.2.2 Shear measurement error budgets

The multiplicative error m in shear measurement propagates directly to a fractional error $2m$ in the cosmic-shear power spectrum. Particularly pernicious are multiplicative shear errors that vary as a function of source redshift, since most of the power of cosmic-shear experiments comes from tomographic analyses of detailed comparison between shear strength on different bins of source redshift. Huterer et al. (2006) (hereafter HTBJ) calculate the degradation of cosmological constraints for the DES and LSST cosmic-shear surveys due to multiplicative shear calibration errors with unknown redshift dependence. From their Figure 4 (reproduced in this thesis in Figure 1.5) we can infer that a systematic error in m of 0.008 (0.003) for DES (LSST) will raise the experiment's uncertainty in the dark-energy equation-of-state parameter w by a factor of $\sqrt{2}$ above the purely statistical errors. [It takes $\approx 5\times$ larger m

values to double the cosmological errors above the statistical uncertainties.] Amara and Réfrégier (2008) carry out a similar analysis, concluding that $|m| < 0.001$ is required for a space-based cosmic-shear survey somewhat more ambitious than LSST, consistent with HTBJ at factor-of-2 level. Since atmospheric dispersion is just one of several potential sources of shear calibration error, an experimental error budget would likely need to hold the contribution from atmospheric dispersion to $\leq \frac{1}{2}$ of the total value in HTBJ. We can hence set a requirement that

$$\left| \left\langle \frac{\Delta V}{r^2} \right\rangle \right| < \begin{cases} 0.004 & \text{(DES)} \\ 0.0015 & \text{(LSST)} \end{cases} \quad (4.12)$$

Placing limits on additive shear errors is more complex because the limits on c depend strongly on how the additive signals correlate across redshift bins. We can make a crude estimate, however, as follows: first, we note that the RMS value of cosmic shear is ≈ 0.02 , so the integrated shear power spectrum is $\langle \gamma^2 \rangle \approx 4 \times 10^{-4}$. The maximum tolerable LSST multiplicative shear error of $m < 0.003$ produces an error in the integrated power spectrum of $2m\langle \gamma^2 \rangle \approx 2.4 \times 10^{-6}$. Spurious shear should not generate power larger than this value, $\langle c^2 \rangle < 2.4 \times 10^{-6}$, suggesting that we need

$$c_{\text{RMS}} < 0.0015. \quad (4.13)$$

If we again allocate half of this error budget to atmospheric dispersion, and keep in mind that the dispersion generates $c_1 = m/2$, we find that the limits on ΔV induced by additive shear are very similar to those induced by multiplicative shear (Equation [4.12]).

One issue that is more severe for additive shear than for multiplicative is that, for multiplicative errors, we are only sensitive to the mean m over all galaxies in a given redshift slice (Guzik and Bernstein, 2005), whereas for c it is the variance across the sky, not the mean value, that is of particular concern. So we should be alert to aspects of the atmospheric dispersion systematic that will cause spurious shear fluctuating on the ~ 10 arcmin scales that carry most cosmic-shear information. For instance, if

ΔV depends on source galaxy type within a redshift bin, we must be concerned that there will be variations in c across the field as the mean background type fluctuates.

4.2.3 Requirements on atmospheric dispersion errors

Our final step in setting requirements on ΔV is to estimate the galaxy size to be used in Equation (4.12). The DES sets a goal of ~ 10 lensing source galaxies per arcmin². Jouvel et al. (2009) produce a model of the background galaxy population sizes and colors using HST/COSMOS and other observations; from this catalog we note that there are 10 galaxies arcmin⁻² with half-light radii $r \geq 0''.4$, hence the *largest* possible value of $\langle 1/r^2 \rangle$ for DES would be to use this population. LSST is more ambitious, with a target source density of 30 arcmin⁻², which will require reaching down to galaxies with $r \geq 0''.27$. For this latter population, $\langle 1/r^2 \rangle \approx (0''.35)^{-2}$. It is also true, however, that many of the galaxies above these cutoff r values will be unusable for weak lensing (due to being too faint, too crowded, or featuring poor photo-z's) which will force the surveys to use galaxies smaller than these best-case cutoff sizes. As a rough guess, we therefore adopt estimates of $\langle 1/r^2 \rangle = (0''.4)^{-2}$ for DES and $(0''.27)^{-2}$ for LSST. The estimated requirements on ΔV for the target galaxy population are therefore

$$|\langle \Delta V \rangle| < \begin{cases} 6 \times 10^{-4} \text{ arcsec}^2 & (\text{DES}) \\ 1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ arcsec}^2 & (\text{LSST}) \end{cases} \quad (4.14)$$

Finally we consider requirements on $\Delta \bar{R}$, for galaxies where different exposures must be registered for shape measurement. In this case the mis-registration will cause a blurring of the galaxy that will be roughly equivalent to an added dispersion $\Delta V \approx \langle (\Delta \bar{R})^2 \rangle$. The details will depend upon the distribution of filters and zenith angles that one is trying to stack, but we can expect this variation to be of the same order as $\Delta \bar{R}$ itself. So we set rough requirements that $\langle (\Delta \bar{R})^2 \rangle$ be below the ΔV

requirements in Equation (4.14), or:

$$\Delta\bar{R}_{\text{RMS}} < \begin{cases} 25 \text{ mas} & (\text{DES}) \\ 10 \text{ mas} & (\text{LSST}) \end{cases} \quad (4.15)$$

An additional point to make here is that two galaxies with opposite signs of $\Delta\bar{R}$ are both elongated in the same direction after stacking, hence our requirement is not on the population mean of $\Delta\bar{R}$; it is on the RMS value of $\Delta\bar{R}$ of individual galaxies. Galaxies with negative $\Delta\bar{R}$ do not cancel the spurious shear of those with $\Delta\bar{R} > 0$.

To summarize, atmospheric refraction has the potential to significantly bias the results of cosmic-shear measurements whenever the stellar calibration results in errors for galaxies exceed *any* of the following limits:

1. The dispersion error $\langle\Delta V\rangle$ of the galaxy population varies with redshift or other binning criteria by an amount exceeding $6(1) \times 10^{-4}$ arcsec² for DES (LSST). This produces a multiplicative shear error that is too large.
2. The galaxy-to-galaxy variation in ΔV within a redshift bin substantially exceeds the above values, which could produce an additive shear fluctuating on arcminute scales that biases the cosmic shear power spectrum.
3. The galaxy-by-galaxy error in refraction centroid $\Delta\bar{R}_{\text{RMS}}$ acquires typical value exceeding 25 (10) mas in any redshift bin for DES (LSST). If this occurs, then stacks of images taken at different airmasses and/or filters will be misregistered and both multiplicative and additive shear errors will be produced.

4.3 Atmospheric dispersion calculation methods

To quantify the effects of refraction on astronomical images, we first write the refraction angle as

$$R(\lambda, z_a) = h(\lambda)g(z_a) \quad (4.16)$$

where $h(\lambda)$ and $g(z_a)$ encode its dependence on wavelength and altitude angle. As indicated by Cox et al. (2001), $g(z_a)$ can be approximated as $g(z_a) = \tan(z_a)$. This functional form implies that $\Delta\bar{R}$ and ΔV scale as $\tan(z_a)$ and $\tan^2(z_a)$, respectively. We will present results assuming $z_a = 45^\circ$, since they are simple ($\tan 45^\circ = 1$) and the ΔV for a particular field of some survey should be scaled by $\langle \tan^2 z_a \rangle$. The required scaling factor for DES is not, however, far from unity, so we will ignore it: we take a simulation of all the DES pointings produced by its scheduling software OBSTAC⁴ and bin them by declination. Figure 4.1 shows the relevant quantity $\langle \tan^2 z_a \rangle$ vs declination expected for DES, showing that $\langle \tan^2 z_a \rangle$ is within about 20% of unity across the declination range of the survey. For LSST, Figure 3.3 of the *LSST Science Book*⁵ suggests that the LSST *i*-band observations have $\langle \tan^2 z_a \rangle \approx 0.6$, so we can expect that the northern and southern extremes of the survey will have $\langle \tan^2 z_a \rangle$ at or above 0.8, slightly below our nominal value of unity.

The calculation of shear artifacts induced by $\Delta\bar{R}$ in a stacking analysis is more complex, because $\Delta\bar{R}$ is actually a vector quantity and the direction to zenith will vary with hour angle of observations of a given field. The deleterious effects will scale with the two-dimensional variance of the $\Delta\bar{R}$ vectors over the course of the survey, so the relevant scaling factor will depend upon the hour-angle distribution as well as zenith-angle distribution, but will be $\leq \langle \tan^2 z_a \rangle$. Our assumption of unity for this scaling factor is hence conservative, but we will see below that the shear systematics from ΔV are larger than those from $\Delta\bar{R}$ even with this conservative upper bound on $\Delta\bar{R}$.

We make use of values for $h(\lambda)$ tabulated in Cox et al. (2001), slightly corrected to take into account the average conditions of pressure and temperature (770 millibar and 11 C, respectively (Stefanik, 2007)) at Cerro Tololo, Chile (DES).

⁴Provided by Eric Neilsen (Neilsen, 2012)

⁵<http://www.lsst.org/lsst/scibook>

Figure 4.1: $\langle \tan^2 z_a \rangle$ for *DES* exposures binned by field declination. The exposure lists are produced by simulations of the full *DES* survey using historical weather patterns and the *OBS*TAC survey planning software (Nielsen, 2012).

As can be readily seen in Equations (4.1) and (4.2), \bar{R} and V both depend on the spectrum of the source object, $S(\lambda)$. To make our calculations, we use the empirical galaxy Spectral Energy Distribution (SED) templates of Coleman et al. (1980) (CWW) and Kinney et al. (1996)⁶. The CCW templates consist of 4 galaxies of type

⁶These spectra are extended in the UV and IR regions by means of the synthetic Bruzual and

E, Im, Scb, Scd and the Kinney templates are representative of both quiescent and starburst galaxies. For the stellar spectra, we utilize the libraries provided by Pickles (1998). We calculate the values of \bar{R} and V for each stellar spectral type, and for galaxy types at values of redshift $z \in [0, 1]$ with $\Delta z = 0.02$, according to Equations (4.1) and (4.2). Then, taking a G5V stellar template as our reference mean stellar spectrum, we calculate $\Delta\bar{R}$ and ΔV for each object in each of the four *griz* filters and compare our results to the requirements for cosmic shear derived in Section 4.2.

4.4 Results for stellar and galactic spectra

The top panels of Figures 4.2 and 4.3 show the calculated values of $\Delta\bar{R}$ and ΔV in the *g* filter as a function of redshift (at $z_a = 45^\circ$). The remaining panels show these same quantities after applying a correction linear in color that will be described in the next section. Similar calculations and plots were performed and obtained in the *r*, *i*, and *z* filters. The results for stellar spectra at $z = 0$ show how the effect of atmospheric refraction is greater for bluer sources, as expected. DES (LSST) requirements, as calculated in Equations (4.14) and (4.15), are also shown in the plots. To determine whether these requirements are satisfied, we first examine the galaxies expected to be detected by the DES according to the DES Data Challenge 6B.⁷ To each of the $\approx 250,000$ galaxies detected in a 10 deg^2 subsample of the simulation we assign a ΔV and $\Delta\bar{R}$ from the template that most closely matches its colors and redshift. Then we divide the galaxy population into four redshift bins, computing the mean value and the dispersion of ΔV and the RMS value of $\Delta\bar{R}$ among the galaxy population. These are represented by the blue circular dots in Figures 4.6 and 4.7 (we assume that the LSST population has similar type distribution to the DES population).

Charlot (1993) spectra.

⁷Simulations created by the DES Data Management Project <http://cosmology.illinois.edu/DES/main/>

Figure 4.2: The differential centroid shift $\Delta\bar{R}$ as a function of redshift ($\Delta z = 0.02$) in the g filter, for zenith angle 45° . Standard templates of galaxies from CWW (Coleman et al., 1980) (E, Sb, Sc, Im galaxies) and Kinney (Kinney et al., 1996) (quiescent—Sa, Sb—and starburst—SB, SB6—galaxies) were used. Pickles (1998) provides templates of stellar spectra (“ukxxyy” labels). A G5V spectrum was used as the reference to set $\Delta\bar{R} = 0$. The top panel shows the $\Delta\bar{R}$ values for each spectrum at different values of z , whereas the lower panels show the same values after applying a linear correction in color, as described in the text. DES (LSST) requirements are that $\Delta\bar{R}_{\text{RMS}}$ fall within the light grey (dark grey) shaded region (Equation [4.15]).

It can be seen that cosmic shear measurements performed in g band will, in the absence of some correction scheme, have systematic errors due to atmospheric

dispersion that dominate the statistical errors, with ΔV up to $6\times$ our threshold of importance for DES and $30\times$ for LSST. The $\Delta\bar{R}_{\text{rms}}$ values are also large enough to cause dominant systematic errors, but ΔV induces worse problems, so we will focus on ΔV henceforth. In r band, the levels of ΔV and $\Delta\bar{R}_{\text{RMS}}$ remain large enough to dominate the LSST error budget but are $1.6\times$ our nominal threshold for DES systematic errors, so may be acceptable for DES. For LSST, even in i band, the dispersion effects are up to $2.6\times$ larger than our derived requirements, so might be subdominant to statistical errors if our various approximations have been too conservative. But certainly the refraction effect requires attention in constructing an LSST error budget. Atmospheric dispersion is not a problem for either experiment in z -band (and we have verified that this is also true, as expected, in Y band).

4.5 Strategies for calibrating effects of atmospheric dispersion

The previous section shows that the effects of atmospheric dispersion on shape measurements are non-negligible in the g , r and i filters. As was pointed out above, $\Delta\bar{R}$ and ΔV depend on the spectra of the observed objects, which cannot be measured in a photometric survey like DES. We would like to develop a calibration or correction that depends only on observable quantities, such as the color of the stars and galaxies. We calculate $\Delta\bar{R}$ and ΔV of each star and galaxy at different redshift values and filters, and plot them as a function of color in Figures 4.4 and 4.5. The plots suggest that a function of color can be defined that partially corrects the values of $\Delta\bar{R}$ and ΔV . We determine $\Delta\bar{R}$ and ΔV functions that depend linearly on color and minimize the RMS residuals of the stellar templates—this is an operation that could be done empirically from the observations.

Figure 4.3: The differential PSF second moment ΔV as a function of redshift ($\Delta z = 0.02$) in the g filter at zenith angle 45° . Standard templates of galaxies from CWW (Coleman et al., 1980) (E, Sb, Sc, Im galaxies) and Kinney (Kinney et al., 1996) (quiescent—Sa, Sb—and starburst—SB, SB6—galaxies) were used. Pickles (1998) provides templates of stellar spectra (“ukxxy” labels). A G5V spectrum was used as the reference to define $\Delta V = 0$. The top panel shows the ΔV values for each spectrum at different values of z , whereas the lower panels show the same values after applying a linear correction in color, as described in the text. DES (LSST) requirements are that ΔV fall within the light grey (dark grey) shaded region (Equation [4.14]).

Figure 4.4: $\Delta\bar{R}$ as a function of color for stellar and galaxy spectra at different redshift values ($z \in [0, 1]$ with $\Delta z = 0.02$) for each of the *griz* filters at $z_a = 45^\circ$. The solid green (magenta) line represents a linear fit using only galaxy (stellar) spectra. Requirements for DES (LSST) on $\Delta\bar{R}_{\text{RMS}}$ are shown by the light grey (dark grey) shaded regions.

Figure 4.5: ΔV as a function of color for stellar and galaxy spectra at different redshift values ($z \in [0, 1]$ with $\Delta z = 0.02$) for each of the *griz* filters at $z_a = 45^\circ$. The solid green (magenta) line represents a linear fit using only galaxy (stellar) spectra. Requirements for DES (LSST) on ΔV are shown by the light grey (dark grey) shaded regions.

The star-shaped symbols in Figures 4.6 and 4.7 give the $\Delta \bar{R}_{\text{RMS}}$, and mean and variance of ΔV , for the galaxy templates in 4 redshift bins after application of the star-based linear color correction to the galaxies. A linear function of color that minimizes the RMS residuals of $\Delta \bar{R}$ and ΔV for the *galaxy* templates (crosses in

Figures 4.5 and 4.6) produces a calibration with smaller residuals for galaxies, but note that such a calibration would have to rely on theoretical calculations since ΔV cannot be measured from the data for the galaxies. The linear fits to both stars and galaxies are also shown in Figures 4.4 and 4.5. The $\Delta \bar{R}_{\text{RMS}}$ and ΔV for the galaxies after applying the linear corrections at each filter are shown in Figures 4.6 and 4.7. Either linear correction brings the atmospheric dispersion effects within requirements in the r (i) band for DES (LSST). The LSST r band systematic errors are still above our thresholds of concern after linear color corrections, by factors up to 5 depending on the redshift bin and type of correction. Thus, they must still be considered as important contributors to the LSST error budget; yet, our results suggest that more sophisticated correction schemes could bring atmospheric-dispersion systematics back below statistical errors in this case. For g band, however, the linear corrections still leave errors well above our thresholds in both DES and LSST, and in fact the “corrected” data are worse in most of the redshift bins than uncorrected ones. Also we note that the galaxy-to-galaxy standard deviation of ΔV within a redshift bin is typically much larger than the DES or LSST requirements we have derived, suggesting that spatial variations of the induced additive shear will be an issue. It appears that atmospheric dispersion is likely to create dominant systematic errors in g band, and the surveys should plan on basing cosmic-shear measurements on the redder bands. We have verified that u band is, as expected, even worse than g .

4.6 Conclusion

Atmospheric dispersion can have a significant effect in PSF correction of shape measurements in broadband photometric surveys by affecting the first and second moments of the observed images. If uncorrected, it produces cosmic-shear spurious signals larger than the desired statistical uncertainties for the g and r bands of the DES, and for the g , r , and i bands for LSST. This effect depends on the spectrum of the source and therefore is not easy to correct for.

Figure 4.6: $\Delta\bar{R}_{\text{RMS}}$ in four equally-spaced redshift bins for each of the four *griz* filters when no correction (blue dots), a linear correction in color using only star spectra (magenta stars) and a linear correction using only galaxy spectra (green crosses) is applied. DES (LSST) requirements are that $\Delta\bar{R}_{\text{RMS}}$ fall within the light grey (dark grey) shaded region (Equation [4.15]).

Figure 4.7: ΔV in four equally-spaced redshift bins for each of the four *griz* filters when no correction (blue dots), a linear correction in color using only star spectra (magenta stars), and a linear correction using only galaxy spectra (green crosses) is applied. The vertical bars depict the standard deviation of ΔV between different galaxy templates and redshifts within each bin. They therefore represent the range of variation that the mean ΔV might accrue due to variations in the population mix of galaxies with redshift and with position on the sky. DES (LSST) requirements are that ΔV fall within the light grey (dark grey) shaded regions (Equation [4.14]).

A simple linear correction to the PSF position and size based on the observed color, calibrated empirically from stars or estimated theoretically for galaxies, should

improve calibration of dispersion effects significantly. Even after applying this correction, however, weak lensing measurements in the g band are significantly degraded by dispersion effects for both DES and LSST. Cosmic shear measurements can be performed with images taken in the r band for the accuracy required by DES, but further work will be needed in the case of LSST. Shape and shear measurements in the z and Y band can safely be performed without attention to dispersion corrections.

There are several possible tactics for further reduction of cosmic-shear systematic errors from atmospheric dispersion:

- Use an atmospheric dispersion corrector (ADC) during the imaging. While this option is available for KIDS cosmic-shear surveys being conducted on the VLT Survey Telescope⁸ and for the HyperSuprime Camera to be installed on Subaru⁹, an ADC is not part of the optical designs for DES and LSST.
- Observe at lower zenith angles— $\Delta\bar{R}$ and ΔV scale as $\tan(z_a)$ and $\tan^2(z_a)$, respectively, so would be reduced by factors of $\sqrt{3}$ and 3, respectively, if we were to take nominal zenith angles of 30° instead of the 45° assumed in our calculations. In practice it would not be easy to maintain such low airmasses throughout a large survey, especially if one wants to survey $15,000 \text{ deg}^2$ or more of low-Galactic-latitude sky from the latitudes of $\approx -30^\circ$ of both Cerro Tololo (DES) and Cerro Pachón (LSST).
- Derive a more elaborate correction than the linear fit we have used, *e.g.*, an approach that makes use of multi-color photometry to estimate the full spectrum of each galaxy—which of course is already done in the course of most template-fitting estimators for photometric redshifts. This technique is discussed by Cypriano et al. (2007) in the context of calibrating wavelength-dependent PSF variation across the very broad band planned for the Euclid spacecraft. In the

⁸<http://www.eso.org/public/teles-instr/surveytelescopes/vst.html>

⁹<http://www.naoj.org/>

Euclid case it is telescope diffraction, not atmospheric refraction, that causes the wavelength dependence of the PSF, but the issue is similar.

- One could simulate the full effect in detail to estimate additive and multiplicative corrections that must be applied to the measured shear fields. This approach would have the usual limitations of precision calibration by simulation: it would be accurate only to the extent that the simulation captures the full multivariate distribution of the sizes, shapes, redshifts, and SEDs of galaxies in the true sky. The SED distribution will be particularly challenging to constrain for the faint end of the surveys' target galaxy populations.

It seems likely, therefore, that both DES and LSST can make use of r or redder bands for cosmic-shear surveys, but this will require explicit galaxy-by-galaxy correction for PSF and astrometric dependence on the source spectrum. For DES, we show that a simple linear color correction will suffice, but more work is needed to devise a correction that recovers the full cosmic-shear utility of the LSST r band data.

We note lateral color in telescope optics causes spurious spectrum-dependent cosmic-shear signals in a manner very similar to the atmospheric dispersion that we examine here. As with atmospheric dispersion, it is typical to specify an optical design that keeps this contribution well below the size of the PSF, but this is not a sufficient condition to guarantee that differences between galaxy and stellar spectra produce PSF calibration errors below the requirements of cosmic-shear surveys.

Chapter 5

Conclusion

In this thesis we have studied some of the many systematic errors that currently affect weak gravitational lensing, in the context of the Dark Energy Survey experiment that will start operations in December 2012. Dark energy is one of the main unsolved problems not only in cosmology but in all physics, and weak lensing is one of the most powerful cosmological techniques to learn more about it, provided that the systematic errors are understood, modeled and kept under control. Shear measurement systematics are usually parameterized in terms of multiplicative and additive errors, $\gamma^{\text{est}} - \gamma^{\text{true}} = m\gamma^{\text{true}} + c$. The science objectives of DES demand that $m < 3 \cdot 10^{-4}$ and $c < 4 \cdot 10^{-4}$ over the full area of the survey (5000 sq. deg.). We have investigated systematic errors related to the performance of the DES shear measurement pipeline, the accuracy of the astrometric solution, and atmospheric dispersion, using the DES thresholds on m and c as a reference.

The main shear measurement pipeline in DES is based on the Elliptical Gauss-Laguerre decomposition (or shapelets) described in Bernstein and Jarvis (2002). We created customized simulations that helped us identify areas in parameter space where the pipeline performs as required and where it needs improvement. We established that a convergence rate of $> 99\%$ is needed to avoid the introduction of incompleteness biases above the required accuracy. We found that a $(S/N)_* \gtrsim 70$ is necessary to

satisfy the full-survey requirements of m and c . Simulations show that, in DES, the number of stars per detector with $(S/N)_\star \gtrsim 75$ will be ~ 250 , providing an enough number of stars to properly model the PSF along each CCD. In the same way, anisotropy suppression below the required thresholds is achieved for galaxies with $S/N \gtrsim 45$. Low-noise galaxies with $r \gtrsim 1$ and $\gamma^{\text{true}} \lesssim 0.075$ have a multiplicative error up to 0.006, slightly larger than the 0.004 required by DES. As the noise was increased, the multiplicative errors started to grow larger. The calibration error of the pipeline was found to be $> 1\%$ for galaxies with $S/N \lesssim 50$. This is comparable to previous measurements, and will be sufficient for weak lensing analysis during the $\sim 100 - 250$ sq. deg. area of the DES first season. However, further work (especially in the high-noise regime) needs to be done to achieve the desired 0.1% accuracy.

We then examined the accuracy of the DES astrometric solution. Using simulated and real data, we implemented the test that studies the variation of the astrometric residuals as a function of focal plane positions (*AST-4*). We showed that the software **REMATCH**, developed in the DES weak lensing working group, is able to improve on the DES standard astrometric solution to satisfy the weak lensing requirements on accuracy. In the near future we plan to implement other tests related to measurement of astrometric residual, using this time real data from the Dark Energy Camera.

We also established that uncorrected atmospheric dispersion effects can cause noticeable errors when measuring shapes in g , r , and i bands. Some mitigations strategies consist in observing at lower zenith angles or using corrections that depend on observables such as color. We demonstrated the effectivity of using a correction linear in color, which reduces the errors in the redder bands (r and i) in accordance with the DES requirements (we performed some calculations based on LSST requirements too). However, the errors in g bands are likely to remain high, which leads us to conclude that cosmic shear analyses should be performed in the redder bands.

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